

Beyond Procrustes distances: a multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein distance capturing chirality

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Abstract

Efficiently and robustly analyzing shape data is critical across many scientific disciplines. While chirality is a fundamental property in numerous applications—most notably in molecular science—existing shape analysis metrics fail to distinguish between a shape and its mirror image. To address this gap, we introduce a multilinear generalization of the Gromov–Wasserstein objective. Under mild assumptions, this objective yields a distance on the shape space, represented as probability distributions quotiented by a symmetry group G , that is notably sensitive to chirality for $G = SO(d)$. We establish robustness properties of the proposed distance and develop efficient algorithms to compute it, reformulating the problem by projecting couplings onto a low-dimensional space. We derive algorithms for both local and approximate global solutions, yielding a fully polynomial-time approximation scheme for this class of multilinear Gromov–Wasserstein problems. We validate the framework through numerical experiments that demonstrate the effectiveness of CGW as a shape metric for chiral objects.

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Keywords.

Shape analysis | Chirality | Optimal transport | Gromov-Wasserstein distance | Procrustes-Wasserstein distance

1 Introduction

Analyzing shape data efficiently and robustly with appropriate metrics is critical across disciplines, including archaeology, medicine, biology, or chemistry [10]. In the context of pharmacology and chemistry, the chirality of molecules can be key to their interactions with other species. For example, D-penicillamine is a drug used to treat rheumatoid arthritis, whereas its reflected version (L-penicillamine) is a toxic compound [38]. Similarly, most amino-acids have a specific chirality [19]. Yet, the standard Procrustes distance [1] does not distinguish between two chiral shapes, which led us to ask: how to build a metric that can efficiently distinguish such chiral objects, or more generally, be sensitive to relevant classes of shape transforms?

To mathematically formalize this problem, we are representing shapes using probability measures on $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ ($d = 2$ or 3) with finite second moment, i.e. elements of $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$. A natural distance on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ is the 2-Wasserstein distance coming from the theory of *Optimal Transport* (OT):

$$W_2(\mu, \nu) := \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\int \|x - y\|^2 d\pi \right)^{1/2}, \quad (\text{W}_2)$$

36 where $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ is the set of couplings between μ and ν , two elements of $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$. To define a proper
 37 shape metric, we can make this distance invariant under rigid body transformations, by quotienting
 38 W_2 under the action of $O(d)$. This yields the *standard Procrustes-Wasserstein distance*, which
 39 has applications in image analysis, natural language processing and computer vision [1, 18, 46] as
 40 well as protein alignment [20]. More generally, we can define a *Procrustes-Wasserstein* distance on
 41 $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})/G$ for any group G of spatial transformations (e.g. $SO(d)$, $E(d)$, $SL(d)$...) as

$$PW_G(\mu, \nu) = \inf_{g \in G} W_2(g\# \mu, \nu), \quad (PW_G)$$

42 where $g\# \mu$ is the pushforward of μ by the map g . The standard Procrustes-Wasserstein problem can
 43 notably be solved for a fixed coupling or a fixed orthogonal transformation [18], but global solutions
 44 are hard to obtain in practice, since they require solving a non-convex optimization problem [18].
 45 Local optimization algorithms have been proposed but their performance is sensitive to initial values
 46 [1, 46]. Globally solving the problem has also been tackled using stochastic optimization, convex
 47 relaxation [18] or for a finite set of invariances G [32]. However, to our knowledge no guarantee of
 48 convergence, or convergence rate for global optimization, has been proved for this problem. In this
 49 framework, distinguishing chiral shapes also requires using $G = SO(d)$ instead of $O(d)$, leading to
 50 similar computational challenges.

51 As an alternative to Procrustes-type distances, one can use a distance that is by construction
 52 directly invariant by group action, bypassing the need to optimize on it. This is achieved for
 53 $G = E(d)$ with the *2-Gromov-Wasserstein* distance:

$$GW_2(\mu, \nu) := \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\int \left(\|x_1 - x_2\|^2 - \|y_1 - y_2\|^2 \right)^2 d\pi(x_1, y_1)\pi(x_2, y_2) \right)^{1/2}. \quad (GW_2)$$

54 This distance was introduced as a way to compare measure metric spaces up to isometries [29, 39],
 55 and its variants have recently been used in various applications, including aligning brain images
 56 [41], proteins [40], or comparing graphs [2, 7] and structured objects [43]. From a computational
 57 aspect, computing the GW distance amounts to solving a concave quadratic programming problem,
 58 and is thus NP-hard in general [34]. Additionally, the GW_2 distance can be generalized by replacing
 59 the Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|$ with any similarity/cost function (e.g. inner product). Recently, the *Inner*
 60 *Gromov-Wasserstein* (IGW) distance was hence introduced using the inner product as similarity
 61 [2, 42]. Using this $O(d)$ invariant pseudo-distance, we can equip $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ with a Riemannian metric
 62 [47], allowing one to define gradient flows, interpolate between shapes, and perform statistical
 63 analysis.

64 In this paper, we propose a general framework, which extends the Gromov-Wasserstein distance,
 65 to define and compute a class of distances over shapes that are sensitive to specific transforms. This
 66 importantly includes $SE(d)$, with a resulting distance capturing chirality that we call the *Chiral*
 67 *Gromov-Wasserstein* (CGW) distance. To define such distances, we first introduce in Section
 68 2 a family of multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein discrepancies, and demonstrate that under some
 69 assumptions, they yield proper distances on shapes. Furthermore, we characterize in this section
 70 their low dimensional structure, study their stability with respect to variation of their argument and
 71 prove the existence of an optimal correspondence map between shapes. In Section 3 we leverage
 72 this low dimensional structure to propose an algorithm that globally solves the GW_m problem.
 73 We show that this algorithm is a fully polynomial time approximation scheme, providing, to our
 74 knowledge, the first estimation of complexity for globally solving a Gromov-Wasserstein type of
 75 problem. As our algorithm makes GW_m distances suitable for practical shape comparison, we run

76 various numerical experiments in Section 4, including comparisons of chiral molecules that highlight
 77 the potential use of CGW as a shape metric.

78 2 Multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein distances and their fun- 79 damental properties

80 We are interested in studying a class of (pseudo-)distances between probability measures that are
 81 invariant by the action of a matrix Lie group $G \subset GL(d)$. Proofs of this section can be found in
 82 Supplementary A. Let $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ with non-empty interior and let us denote as $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$, the set of
 83 probability measures on \mathcal{X} with finite second moment. We also consider the action of G on \mathcal{X} as
 84 the map $(g, x) \in G \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow g(x) \in \mathcal{X}$.

85 **Definition 1.** Given a map $g : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, we denote $g^{\times n} : (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathcal{X}^n \rightarrow (g(x_1), \dots, g(x_n)) \in$
 86 \mathcal{Y}^n . A function f on \mathcal{X}^n is invariant by the action of G (or G -invariant) if: $\forall g \in G, f = f \circ g^{\times n}$.

87 **Definition 2.** We define a G -shape as a probability distribution up to the action of G , i.e. an
 88 element of the G -shape space $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})/G$, associated with the action $(g, \mu) \in G \times \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X}) \mapsto g\#\mu$.

89 Note that this definition differs from the classical definition of shapes [10, 23] which are invari-
 90 ant by rigid transformation, scaling and re-parametrization. Indeed, our definition is not scaling
 91 invariant for a matrix Lie group G , but it generalizes shapes to other possible types of invariance.
 92 For simplicity, we now refer to G -shapes simply as shapes, where G is specified when relevant.

93 2.1 A distance between shapes

94 We equip the shape space with a discrepancy as follows: Assume that there exists a multilinear
 95 n -form (or n -tensor) m over \mathcal{X} , that is invariant by G , and such that G can be written as

$$G = G_m := \{T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d, m = m \circ T^{\times n}\},$$

96 the group of transformations preserving the form m . In Lemma 2, we give a sufficient non-
 97 degeneracy condition on m such that $G_m \subset GL(d, \mathbb{R})$, guaranteeing that we have a matrix Lie
 98 group. Examples of such Lie groups and multilinear forms are: $O(d)$ and $U(d)$ with $m = \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ the
 99 standard inner product; and $SL(d)$ with $m = \det$. Now, we define the G -invariant discrepancy:

100 **Definition 3.** Given a multilinear n -form m on \mathbb{R}^d , $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, and $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X}) \times \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$, we
 101 define the *multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein* discrepancy as:

$$\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) := \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \right)^{1/2}, \quad (\text{GW}_m)$$

102 where $\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \prod_{i=1}^n \pi(x_i, y_i)$ and $m(\mathbf{x}) = m(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ with $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^n$. By
 103 construction GW_m is invariant by action of the Lie group G .

104 A classical optimal transport fact, that we will use extensively, is that there exists an optimal
 105 transport plan π for the GW_m problem. This is due to the compactness of the set of coupling
 106 $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ for the weak topology, as proven in Proposition 6.

107 *Remark.* For a finite family of multilinear forms (m) , we can generalize the definition of \mathbf{GW}_m as:

$$\mathbf{GW}_{(m)}(\mu, \nu) := \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\sum_{m_i \in (m)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^{n(m_i)}} (m_i(\mathbf{x}) - m_i(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n(m_i)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \right)^{1/2},$$

108 where $n(m_i)$ is the degree of the form m_i , defining an objective invariant by $G = \bigcap_{m_i \in (m)} G_{m_i}$,
 109 and all the results shown below can be applied to this case. In the following example, we introduce
 110 a chiral distance invariant by $SO(d) = O(d) \cap SL(d) = G_{\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle} \cap G_{\det}$.

111 **Example 1.** We define the Inner Gromov-Wasserstein (IGW), Determinant Gromov-Wasserstein
 112 (DGW) and Chiral Gromov-Wasserstein (CGW) \mathbf{GW}_m discrepancies, that are respectively associ-
 113 ated with $G = O(d)$, $SL(d)$ and $SO(d)$; as

$$\text{IGW}(\mu, \nu) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle - \langle y_1, y_2 \rangle|^2 d\pi^{\otimes 2} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (\text{IGW})$$

$$\text{DGW}(\mu, \nu) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} |\det(\mathbf{x}) - \det(\mathbf{y})|^2 d\pi^{\otimes d} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (\text{DGW})$$

$$\text{CGW}_t(\mu, \nu) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \left(t \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle - \langle y_1, y_2 \rangle|^2 d\pi^{\otimes 2} + (1-t) \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} |\det(\mathbf{x}) - \det(\mathbf{y})|^2 d\pi^{\otimes d} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (\text{CGW})$$

114 Here, the determinant is taken over the d vectors of $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_d)$, with $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and $0 < t < 1$
 115 is a fixed parameter.

116 **Lemma 1.** $\mathbf{GW}_m: (\mu, \nu) \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a pseudo distance.

117 Note that \mathbf{GW}_m is not a distance on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$, since it does not separate points. For example
 118 $\mathbf{GW}_m(\mu, g\sharp\mu) = 0$ for $g \in G$ by construction. Under some assumptions, \mathbf{GW}_m is actually a distance
 119 between G -shapes (Propositions 3 and 4). By definition, \mathbf{GW}_m is also not translation invariant,
 120 but we can easily make it the case by centering the marginals. More precisely, for $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$, let us
 121 denote the shift map $S_z : x \in \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto x + z$ and consider the following objective:

$$\inf_{\substack{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu) \\ t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d}} C(\pi, t, u) = \inf_{\substack{\pi \in \Pi(S_{t\sharp}\mu, S_{u\sharp}\nu) \\ t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d}} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}), \quad (1)$$

122 with $C(\pi, t, u) = \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{i}_n(t)) - m(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{i}_n(u))]^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}$ and $\mathbf{i}_n : x \in \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto (x, \dots, x) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^n$.

123 **Proposition 1.** Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ with respective mean $\bar{\mu}, \bar{\nu}$, and π an optimal solution to the
 124 problem $\mathbf{GW}_m(S_{-\bar{\mu}\sharp}\mu, S_{-\bar{\nu}\sharp}\nu)$ (i.e. with centered marginal). Then $(\pi, -\bar{\mu}, -\bar{\nu})$ is a solution of
 125 problem (1).

126 A consequence of Proposition 1, is that centering the marginal is a natural way of defining
 127 a translation invariant metric, since it corresponds to a Procrustes distance with respect to the
 128 translations. Let's now consider the effect of marginal scaling on the \mathbf{GW}_m problem. For $\alpha > 0$,

129 we define the scaling-by- α function $U_\alpha : x \in \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \alpha x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. We also define $\text{id}_X : (x, y) \in X \times Y \mapsto$
130 $x \in X$ and similarly for id_Y . The GW_m cost is not scaling invariant, but the optimal transport
131 plan scales with the marginals in the following sense:

132 **Proposition 2.** *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{P}_2(X), \nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(Y)$ and π^* be an optimal solution of the $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$
133 problem. A solution of the $\text{GW}_m(\mu, U_\alpha \# \nu)$ problem is $(\text{id}_X, U_\alpha \circ \text{id}_Y) \# \pi^*$. More generally, the
134 pushforward by $(\text{id}_X, U_\alpha \circ \text{id}_Y)$ is a one to one correspondence between solutions of $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ and
135 $\text{GW}_m(\mu, U_\alpha \# \nu)$.*

136 This proposition has some practical implications, avoiding the need to rescale or normalize
137 shapes when doing registration or matching. Indeed, once an optimal coupling between two dis-
138 tributions is known, then we can easily deduce an optimal coupling between rescaled shapes. For
139 instance, in a discrete setting where the indexing of the space (x_j vs. αx_j) is the same, the optimal
140 correspondence is identical, and the optimal objective value for any α can be evaluated with the
141 invariant optimal correspondence. We now provide sufficient conditions for GW_m to define a proper
142 distance. We first introduce a condition on m , which we term non-degeneracy:

143 **Definition 4.** Let m be a multilinear n -form on \mathbb{R}^d . We say that m is non-degenerate at slot i if,
144 for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^d \setminus \{0\}$, $m(\dots, x, \dots) \neq 0$ as an $n - 1$ form. We say that m is non-degenerate if there
145 exists an index i such that m is non-degenerate at slot i .

146 *Remark.* The inner product and the determinant are non-degenerate. Indeed, given $x \in \mathbb{R}^d \setminus \{0\}$,
147 $\langle x, x \rangle = \|x\|^2 > 0$, and we can complete $\{x\}$ to a basis $\{x, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}\}$ of \mathbb{R}^d , such that
148 $\det(x, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}) \neq 0$.

149 The non-degeneracy condition then allows us to characterize the applications $T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, such
150 that m is T -invariant. T is in fact a linear invertible map:

151 **Lemma 2.** *Let m be a non-degenerate n -form on \mathbb{R}^d and $T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$. Then $m = m \circ T^{\times n} \implies$
152 $T \in \text{GL}(d)$.*

153 Using this, we can prove that GW_m is a distance (up to the action of G) on both (compactly
154 supported) absolutely continuous measures, and positive volume point clouds of the same size.

155 **Proposition 3.** *Let m be a non-degenerate n -form on \mathbb{R}^d , $X \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be compact and $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(X)$.
156 If μ has a density, then we have the following equivalence: $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \exists g \in G, \mu = g \# \nu$.*

157 **Proposition 4.** *Let m be a non-degenerate n -form on \mathbb{R}^d . Let μ, ν be two points clouds of size k ,
158 i.e. we can write them as $\frac{1}{k} \sum_1^k \delta_{z_i}$, with $z_i \neq z_j$ for $i \neq j$. We also assume that they have non-zero
159 volume, i.e. that there exists a basis of \mathbb{R}^d , $z_1, \dots, z_d \in \text{supp}(\mu)$. Then we have the following
160 equivalence: $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \exists g \in G, \mu = g \# \nu$.*

161 **Corollary 1.** *Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)_{\text{ac}}^{\text{cp}}$ be the set of probability measures on \mathbb{R}^d with a density and a compact
162 support. Let $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathbb{R}^d)$ be the set of point clouds of size k . After centering the marginal, we have that:*

- 163 **IGW** is a distance on $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)_{\text{ac}}^{\text{cp}}/E(d)$, and on $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathbb{R}^d)/E(d)$.
- 164 **DGW** is a distance on $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)_{\text{ac}}^{\text{cp}}/(SL(d) \rtimes T_r(d))$, and on $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathbb{R}^d)/(SL(d) \rtimes T_r(d))$.
- 165 **CGW** is a distance on $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)_{\text{ac}}^{\text{cp}}/SE(d)$, and on $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathbb{R}^d)/SE(d)$.

166 Here \rtimes denotes the group semidirect product and $T_r(d)$ the group of translations in \mathbb{R}^d .

167 As a result of Corollary 1, the GW_m distance can be used to compare shapes in practical
 168 applications, specifically when they are represented as point clouds. Note that the multilinear
 169 form m , and thus, the group G can be appropriately chosen for a specific application, e.g. the
 170 CGW distance for distinguishing chirality between proteins and molecules. Next, we address the
 171 challenge of computing the shape metric, by revealing the low dimensional structure of the GW_m
 172 optimization problem, that will then be leveraged to derive an efficient algorithm in Section 3.

173 2.2 Characterization of the multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein problem 174 with the covariance matrix

175 We are now interested in solving the multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein problem i.e, computing dis-
 176 tance $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ given μ, ν . As for the classical Gromov-Wasserstein distance, it is a non-convex
 177 polynomial programming problem, NP-hard in general. However, the GW_2 problem admits a low
 178 dimensional structure that can be leveraged to compute approximations of a global solution, as done
 179 in [35]. Similarly, the next results reformulate the GW_m problem as depending only on the projec-
 180 tion of the couplings on a low dimensional space, as represented in Figure 1A. Given $\eta \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$, we
 181 define its covariance matrix $\tilde{\Sigma}^\eta = \int_{\mathcal{X}} xx^T d\eta(x)$. Given $\xi \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ we define its cross-covariance
 182 matrix $\Sigma^\xi = \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} xy^T d\xi(x, y)$.

183 **Proposition 5.** *Let $(\mu, \nu) \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X}) \times \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$ and m be an n -form. The GW_m cost can be written
 184 as a multivariate polynomial only depending on the covariance matrices $\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu, \tilde{\Sigma}^\nu$ of μ, ν , and the
 185 cross-covariance Σ^π of π as*

$$\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 = Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\Sigma^\pi),$$

186 with $Q_m : \mathbb{R}^{d^2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a degree n multi-variate polynomial with d^2 variables, depending on the expan-
 187 sion of m on the canonical basis only. Computation of the polynomial Q_m for specific forms m can
 188 be found in Supplementary A.2. Define the continuous linear map $\tilde{p}_0 : \pi \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}) \mapsto \Sigma^\pi \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$
 189 and $\tilde{P}_\Pi := \tilde{p}_0(\Pi(\mu, \nu))$ a compact convex set. Then:

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) = \inf_{x \in \tilde{P}_\Pi} -Q_m((x^{i,j})_{i,j}), \quad (2)$$

190 with $x^{i,j}$ the coordinates of x on the canonical basis of \mathbb{R}^{d^2} .

191 We now assume that \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} are compact and μ, ν have full dimensional support. We define
 192 $f_{i,j} : (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto x^i y^j \in \mathbb{R}$, where x^i is the i -th component of x , and $V = \text{span}(f_{i,j}) \subset$
 193 $\mathcal{C}_b(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ continuous bounded functions. Note that $\int f_{i,j} d\pi = \Sigma_{i,j}^\pi$ for $\pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$. We equip
 194 V with $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ the $L^2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ inner product. Let's define (e_i) an orthonormal basis of V . Then
 195 $p_0 : \pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}) \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{d^2} e_i \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} e_i d\pi \in V$, is the natural extension from $L^2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ to $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$
 196 of the orthogonal projection over V . In the compact case, we have an equivalent reformulation of
 197 Proposition 5:

198 **Corollary 2.** *For all $v \in V$ and $\pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$, we have $\int v d\pi = \langle v, p_0(\pi) \rangle$. If $\mathcal{R}_f : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ is
 199 the representation of vectors $v \in V$ in the $(f_{i,j})_{i,j}$ basis, then $\tilde{p}_0 = \mathcal{R}_f \circ p_0$. Finally, we can compute
 200 the distance $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ by solving problem (2), which is equivalent to minimizing $Q_m \circ \mathcal{R}_f$ over
 201 the compact convex set $P_\Pi = p_0(\Pi(\mu, \nu))$.*

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) = \inf_{x \in P_\Pi} -Q_m \circ \mathcal{R}_f(x).$$

Figure 1: The low-dimensional structure of the GW_m problem and how it is approximately solved using a sandwich algorithm. A) Low-dimensional structure of the GW_m problem described in Corollary 2. Given a coupling $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$, the optimization problem for computing $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ only depends on the projection of π on a d^2 dimensional space. We reformulate the computation of $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$, as the global optimization over a compact convex set P_Π , of a multi-variable polynomial function Q_m . B) Representation of Kamenev’s sandwich algorithm [21, 26] to geometrically approximate P_Π , as described in Section 3.1. The algorithm recursively updates two bounding boxes P_Π^+ and P_Π^- , which are converging to P_Π . At each iteration, the direction (black arrow) maximizing the gap between the two boxes (black dashed line) is selected. Then a new supporting hyperplane (blue dotted line) and vertex (red star) are computed to update the boxes.

202 In practical applications, the spaces \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} are compact. In Section 3 which covers algorithms
 203 to solve the GW_m problem, we will identify Q_m and $Q_m \circ \mathcal{R}_f$, since it only depends on the base
 204 vectors are represented in. The inner product used on V is the one described in Corollary 2.

205 **Example 2.** For the **IGW** problem, $Q_m = \|\cdot\|_F^2$ the squared Frobenius norm, for the **DGW** problem,
 206 $Q_m = \det$ and for the **CGW** problem with parameter t , $Q_m = t\|\cdot\|_F^2 + (1-t)\det$.

207 *Remark.* Note that a similar low dimensional description holds for the classical 2-Gromov-Wasserstein
 208 problem (with squared Euclidean distance), with a more complex term that does not depend on
 209 the coupling (see Supplementary A.3). This fact is used in [35] to design an algorithm that ap-
 210 proximates the 2-GW distance between measures. In this case, when $\mu \in \mathcal{P}_4(\mathcal{X}), \nu \in \mathcal{P}_4(\mathcal{Y})$ the
 211 polynomial $-Q_m$ to be optimized is concave and depends on the coordinate of vectors of V a vector
 212 space of dimension $d^2 + 1$. We have $V = \text{span}(g, (f_{i,j})_{i,j})$, $g : x, y \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto \|x\|_2^2 \|y\|_2^2$ and
 213 $f_{i,j} : x, y \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto x^i y^j$. The analog of the projection p_0 is still continuous and we can solve
 214 the optimization problem on P_Π , a compact convex subset of dimension $d^2 + 1$. All the results of
 215 this paper, excepted Lemma 3 and Proposition 4 and 3, have variants with similar proofs applying
 216 to the classical 2-Gromov-Wasserstein problem. A stronger result as the two cited propositions
 217 however holds for the 2-Gromov-Wasserstein, as it is a distance on $\mathcal{P}_4(\mathbb{R}^d)/E(d)$ [29, Theorem 5.1].

218 2.3 Properties of the optimal coupling

219 Now we state existence and stability results for the GW_m cost. We are considering the W_2 distance
 220 between couplings. To wit, recall that when $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$, a coupling $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$
 221 is itself an element of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$; and when both μ and ν have finite second moments, so does

222 π . Assuming \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} are each endowed with metrics $D_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $D_{\mathcal{Y}}$, by convention we equip the
 223 product space $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$ with the metric $D_{\mathcal{X}} \oplus D_{\mathcal{Y}}$, defined by

$$D_{\mathcal{X}} \oplus D_{\mathcal{Y}}((x, y), (x', y')) := \sqrt{D_{\mathcal{X}}^2(x, x') + D_{\mathcal{Y}}^2(y, y')}.$$

224 Accordingly, the W_2 metric on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ is defined using $D_{\mathcal{X}} \oplus D_{\mathcal{Y}}$. In other words, given
 225 $\pi, \pi' \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$,

$$W_2^2(\pi, \pi') := \inf_{\Theta \in \Pi(\pi, \pi')} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} (D_{\mathcal{X}}^2(x, x') + D_{\mathcal{Y}}^2(y, y')) d\Theta((x, y), (x', y')).$$

226 The following proposition establishes existence, and qualitative stability, of minimizers of the
 227 multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein problem with respect to W_2 perturbations of the marginals. The
 228 proof is a straightforward application of Γ -convergence techniques (see [5]), but we could not find a
 229 suitable reference: in particular, the corresponding proof of stability for the p -Gromov-Wasserstein
 230 problem in the original paper of Memoli [29] is less direct and does not apply in our case.

231 **Proposition 6.** *Let $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $Q : \mathbb{R}^{d^2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a polynomial with d^2 variables, $\mu \in$
 232 $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$, and consider (μ_k) and (ν_k) respectively converging to μ and ν , such that
 233 $W_2(\mu_k, \mu) \rightarrow 0$ and $W_2(\nu_k, \nu) \rightarrow 0$. Denote $\mathcal{C}(\pi) := Q(\Sigma^\pi)$; then $\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathcal{C}(\pi)$ is attained, and
 234 $\min_{\pi_k \in \Pi(\mu_k, \nu_k)} \mathcal{C}(\pi_k) \rightarrow \min_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathcal{C}(\pi)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.*

235 *Furthermore, letting $\pi_k^* \in \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu_k, \nu_k)} \mathcal{C}(\pi_k)$, it holds that π_k^* is precompact in $(\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times$
 236 $\mathcal{Y}), W_2)$, and any limit point π^* is contained in $\operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathcal{C}(\pi)$.*

237 We now quantify the stability of the GW_m distance with respect to the marginals.

238 **Theorem 1.** *Let $\mu, \mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu, \nu_0 \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$, and assume that their second moment follow
 239 $\mathfrak{m}_2(\mu), \mathfrak{m}_2(\mu_0), \mathfrak{m}_2(\nu), \mathfrak{m}_2(\nu_0) \leq \alpha$ for $\alpha \geq 1$. If n is the degree of the multilinear form m , then we
 240 have:*

$$|\operatorname{GW}_m(\mu_0, \nu_0)^2 - \operatorname{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2| \leq (2 + 4\sqrt{2})c_1\alpha^{n-1/2}(W_2(\mu_0, \mu) + W_2(\nu_0, \nu)), \quad (3)$$

241 with c_1 the ℓ^1 norm of the coefficients of the polynomial Q_m .

242 This theorem can be used in practical cases to approximate the GW_m distance given a specific
 243 tolerance, for example when a downsampling of the marginals is needed. Typically, if μ and ν are
 244 discrete marginals with a large number of points, one can approximate the marginals with fewer
 245 points, then solve the GW_m problem on the approximation, and estimate the resulting error in
 246 cost.

247 *Remark.* Note that, when μ, ν have finite q moments for q large enough ($q > 4$ if $d \leq 2$ else
 248 $q > 2d/(d-2)$), we can apply Theorem 1 to classical W_2 convergence rates of the empirical
 249 distributions with k elements $\hat{\mu}_k, \hat{\nu}_k$ [15] to get

$$\mathbb{E}[|\operatorname{GW}_m(\hat{\mu}_k, \hat{\nu}_k)^2 - \operatorname{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2|] \leq c\alpha^{n-1/2}\phi_k,$$

250 with $\phi_k = k^{-\frac{1}{\max(d,4)}} \ln(k)^{\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{1}_{\{d=4\}}}$. Here the constant c only depends on the q -th moment of the
 251 marginals, the multilinear form m and the dimension d . Similar result holds with different rates
 252 under weaker assumptions on q . Our rate is worse than the ones derived for the GW_2 distance
 253 [48, Theorem 4.2] and [22, Theorem 3.1], which are leveraging the existence of a variational formul-
 254 ulation for the concave GW_2 cost [48, Corollary 4.1]. However, our results apply to more general
 255 costs, which may be non-concave (they are never convex) and may not possess such variational
 256 formulation. For example the DGW cost is not concave.

257 **Definition 5.** We call a *Monge map* an optimal solution of an optimal transport problem that can
 258 be written $\pi = (\text{id}, T)_{\#}\mu$, with $T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ a measurable map (called the optimal correspondence
 259 map). In particular, the marginal constraints on π imply $\nu = T_{\#}\mu$, and T represents how to move
 260 the mass of μ to ν in an optimal way.

261 The existence of Monge maps has been studied in different settings, but is not guaranteed in full
 262 generality: characterizing this existence for the squared Euclidean Gromov-Wasserstein distance is
 263 still an open problem [12]. Its existence for the W_2 problem, when the first marginal μ has a density
 264 has been proved [6], and it is a fundamental result in optimal transport theory. We now extend the
 265 existence of Monge map to GW_m problems by adapting an argument from [12, Theorem 3.2].

266 **Lemma 3** (Existence of a Monge map for GW_m). *Suppose that $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ have compact support
 267 and that $\mu \ll \text{Leb}$, i.e. μ has a density. Then there exists an optimal correspondence map $T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow$
 268 \mathbb{R}^d . Thus, the optimal transport plan for the GW_m problem can be written as $(\text{id}, T)_{\#}\mu$. Moreover,
 269 any optimal transport plan is a Monge map.*

270 Proposition 6 and Theorem 1 show the stability of the GW_m cost and optimal coupling, when
 271 the marginals μ, ν are approximated. In particular, this applies when the marginals have a density
 272 and are approximated by a discrete measure (in numerical applications for example): The discrete
 273 cost converges towards the continuous cost, at a controlled rate. The existence of a Monge map
 274 establishes an optimal correspondence between marginals in the continuous setting. When numer-
 275 ically approximated, such a map enables shape alignment and registration. Note that, for general
 276 marginals μ, ν , the optimal plans may not be maps, and that the convergence of the optimal plans
 277 happens up to a subsequence, since the GW_m may have several solutions.

278 3 Solving multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein problems in low 279 dimension

280 We are presenting in this section an algorithm that approximates the global solution of the GW_m
 281 problem, leveraging its low dimensional structure (Corollary 2). We consider the case where the
 282 marginals μ, ν have finite support and we assume that their dimension d is low, typically 2 or 3.
 283 Proofs for this section and additional algorithms can be found in Supplementary B. Our algorithm
 284 is structured as follows:

- 285 (i) [Section 3.1] We approximate the projection P_{Π} of the marginal constraint space $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$
 286 on the low dimensional space V . This is done with a sequential refinement of upper and lower
 287 polytopes for P_{Π} , called bounding boxes. They converge to P_{Π} at a known rate (see Theorem 2).
- 288 (ii) [Section 3.2] Once bounding boxes have converged to a given precision, we solve the poly-
 289 nomial optimization problem $\inf -Q_m(x)$ on the bounding boxes. We obtain two values that are
 290 lower and upper bounds for the optimal cost on P_{Π} . They can also be computed at each iteration
 291 and be used as a certificate of global optimality.
- 292 (iii) [Section 3.4] In order to converge to a local optimum of our problem, we propose a reformu-
 293 lation of the Frank-Wolfe scheme (Algorithm 3) that also leverages the low-dimensional structure
 294 of the problem. This local optimization is initialized using the approximation of a global minimum
 295 computed in step (ii).

296 In Section 3.3, we study the case of a concave cost. This enables us to perform the optimization
 297 step (ii) efficiently using the polytope representation of the bounding boxes, and to compute the

298 optimal coupling as a solution to an optimal transport problem. When the cost is concave, GW_m
 299 distances can be practically computed between large data, as our algorithm is tractable (see The-
 300 orem 3). We also show that the complexity arising from the data size only corresponds to solving
 301 classical optimal transport problems.

302 Our algorithm shares similarities with a recent approach for globally solving the 2-Gromov-
 303 Wasserstein problem [35], and our algorithm can also solve this classical GW problem. One major
 304 difference in our approach resides in the choice of direction of the cuts for updating the bounding
 305 boxes. In our case, the directions derive from solving an optimization problem with respect to both
 306 inner and outer bounding boxes, while in [35] they were computed from the gradient of the functional
 307 at an optimum of the outer bounding box. Note that this allows us to derive a convergence rate
 308 for our concave algorithm (see Theorem 2), whereas only the convergence of the algorithm could
 309 previously be obtained. In addition, our algorithm applies in a more general setting to weighted
 310 point clouds, and includes a local optimization step that is key for the convergence of the transport
 311 plan (see Section 3.4). Numerical comparison of Ryner’s et al. algorithm [35] and ours can be found
 312 in Figure 6.

313 3.1 A Sandwich algorithm to approximate polytopes

314 We now present a method to approximate P_Π . When the marginals are discretized, a direct com-
 315 putation of P_Π naturally suffers the curse of dimensionality, because it would require projecting all
 316 extremal points of $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ over V . Instead, we are iteratively approximating P_Π with supporting
 317 hyperplanes by applying Kamenev’s sandwich algorithm [21, 26], as represented in Figure 1B. This
 318 algorithm iteratively creates both a decreasing outer bounding box P_Π^+ and an increasing inner
 319 bounding box P_Π^- . More precisely, at iteration k , $P_{\Pi,k}^- \subset P_\Pi \subset P_{\Pi,k}^+$ and $(P_\Pi^\pm)_k$ are monotone
 320 families of convex sets converging to P_Π as $k \rightarrow +\infty$. The bounding boxes are built as follows:

321 **Definition 6** (Bounding boxes). Let P_Π be a polytope $\subset V$ with boundary ∂P_Π . Then P_Π^- is an
 322 inner bounding box of P_Π if it is the convex hull of points in ∂P_Π and P_Π^+ is an upper bounding
 323 box of P_Π if it is the intersection of supporting half spaces of P_Π .

324 In our algorithm, we are iteratively appending points $g^* := \operatorname{argmax}_{h \in P_\Pi} \langle h, g \rangle \in \partial P_\Pi$ to P_Π^- , for
 325 given directions g . Similarly, we compute $\hat{g} = \max_{h \in P_\Pi} \langle h, g \rangle$ and update the outer bounding box
 326 as follows: $P_\Pi^+ \leftarrow P_\Pi^+ \cap H(g)$, with $H(g) := \{h \in V, \langle h, g \rangle \leq \hat{g}\}$, the supporting hyperplane of P_Π
 327 in direction g .

328 **Definition 7** (Representation of a polytope). A polytope $P \subset \mathbb{R}^l$ can be equivalently represented
 329 by its vertices or its facets. We define the V -representation of P as the convex hull of the set of its
 330 vertices, i.e. $P = \operatorname{conv}(\{x \text{ vertex of } P\})$. We define the H -representation of P as the intersection
 331 of halfspaces: $P = \bigcap_{g \in F(P)} H(g)$ where $F(P)$ is the set of P -facets unit normals vectors pointing
 332 outwards. Each facet is a linear constraint for the feasible set P . The H -representation of a
 333 polytope with s facets can be written as $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^l, Ax \leq b\}$, with A a $s \times l$ matrix and b a vector of
 334 size s , where each row represents a constraint.

335 At each iteration k of the algorithm, a unit vector g_k is chosen (see below). We then solve the
 336 linear program:

$$\hat{g}_k, g_k^* = \max, \operatorname{argmax}_{h \in P_\Pi} \langle h, g \rangle, \quad \text{with} \quad \max_{h \in P_\Pi} \langle h, g \rangle = \max_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} g(x, y) d\pi(x, y), \quad (4)$$

337 and the bounding boxes are updated by adding a vertex to P_{Π}^{-} and a constraint to P_{Π}^{+} , as described
 338 in Definition 6 and below. Note that problem (4) is an optimal transport problem with cost g as a
 339 result of Corollary 2. This problem can be solved or efficiently approximated using various methods
 340 [8, 33, 13, 14, 9]. To choose g_{k+1} , we follow Kamenev’s strategy [26, 21] and maximize the gap
 341 between $P_{\Pi,k}^{-}$ and $P_{\Pi,k}^{+}$, as:

$$c, g_{k+1} = \max, \operatorname{argmax}_{g \in F(P_{\Pi,k}^{-})} \left[\max_{h \in P_{\Pi,k}^{+}} \langle h, g \rangle - \max_{h \in P_{\Pi,k}^{-}} \langle h, g \rangle \right]. \quad (5)$$

342 The value c represents this maximal gap, or a distance between the bounding boxes [26] (black
 343 dashed line in Figure 1B). Note that g_{k+1} is an element of $F(P_{\Pi,k}^{-})$ (see Definition 7), and the value
 344 $\max_{h \in P_{\Pi,k}^{-}} \langle h, g \rangle$ is known in the H -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{-}$. We know the H -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{+}$
 345 and the V -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{-}$ by construction as we append to them the new face and vertex
 346 computed at each iteration, hence they have size $O(k)$. Since a solution of $\operatorname{argmax}_{h \in P_{\Pi,k}^{+}} \langle h, g \rangle$ is
 347 a vertex of $P_{\Pi,k}^{+}$, problem (5) can be efficiently solved using the V -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{+}$ and
 348 the H -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{-}$. Thus, the algorithm requires computing the H -representation of
 349 $P_{\Pi,k}^{-}$ and the V -representation of $P_{\Pi,k}^{+}$, knowing the other representation in each case. By the
 350 Upper Bound Theorem [28, Section 5.5], the newly computed representations have size at most
 351 $k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor}$, so we can control the size of the bounding boxes. The strategy to approximate P_{Π} is
 352 summarized in Algorithm 1, where we initialize the bounding boxes using Algorithm 8 (the impact
 353 of the initialization on convergence will be discussed next). In Figure 1B we also give a schematic
 354 of how the bounding boxes get updated upon selecting the new direction g_{k+1} .

Algorithm 1 Approximation of P_{Π} [21]

Require: $\epsilon > 0, \mu, \nu$ probability measure with finite support.

- 1: Define the gap between the bounding boxes $c = +\infty$
 - 2: **Initialize:** Create bounding boxes P_{Π}^{-}, P_{Π}^{+} such that P_{Π}^{+} is bounded.
 - 3: **while** $c > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 4: Solve (5) and compute c, g
 - 5: Solve (4) with direction g and compute \hat{g}, g^*
 - 6: $P_{\Pi}^{-} \leftarrow \operatorname{conv}(P_{\Pi}^{-} \cup g^*)$
 - 7: $P_{\Pi}^{+} \leftarrow P_{\Pi}^{+} \cap H(g)$
 - 8: **end while**
 - 9: **return** P_{Π}^{-}, P_{Π}^{+}
-

355 We now study the convergence rate of Algorithm 1. We first introduce the Hausdorff distance
 356 between two polytopes $P, Q \subset \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$:

$$\mathcal{H}_2(P, Q) = \max \left(\sup_{x \in Q} \inf_{y \in P} \|x - y\|, \sup_{y \in Q} \inf_{x \in P} \|x - y\| \right). \quad (6)$$

357 Our convergence rate estimation relies on the fact that we can control the volume of the convex
 358 set P_{Π} , assuming that the marginals covariance matrices $\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}^{\nu}$ are definite positive, with the
 359 following notations

360 *Assumption/Notation 1.* We assume μ and ν to be compactly supported and $\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}^{\nu}$ are definite
 361 positive, with $R, \lambda > 0$ such that $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R))$ and $\lambda \leq \min(\operatorname{Spec}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}) \cup \operatorname{Spec}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\nu}))$.

362 Under this assumption, the discrepancy defined in (5) is actually strongly equivalent to \mathcal{H}_2
 363 (from [26, Lemma 4.4] and Lemma 9). Several initializations of the bounding boxes for Algorithm
 364 1 are possible, for example using a d^2 dimensional hyper-rectangle or a d^2 simplex. However, for
 365 Theorem 2 to hold, we need to create an initial bounding box P_{Π}^- with a controlled volume and
 366 asphericity (more details in Supplementary B.1). Algorithm 6 creates such a box.

367 **Theorem 2.** *Let $\epsilon > 0$. Under Assumption 1, suppose that we initialize Algorithm 1 with a*
 368 *bounding box as described in Algorithm 6. Then there exists a constant c_0 depending on d, R and*
 369 *λ only, such that:*

$$\mathcal{H}_2(P_{\Pi,k}^+, P_{\Pi,k}^-) \leq c_0 k^{-1/(d^2-1)}, \text{ for } k \geq d^2 + 1.$$

370 *In other words the bounding boxes $P_{\Pi,k}^+$ and $P_{\Pi,k}^-$ converge to the set P_{Π} at a rate $\frac{1}{d^2-1}$.*

371 3.2 Optimization of the cost

372 As Corollary 2 shows, solving the GW_m problem is equivalent to minimize the polynomial $-Q_m$
 373 on P_{Π} , a d^2 dimensional compact convex set. To approximate this solution, we minimize $-Q_m$ on
 374 the inner bounding box P_{Π}^- as:

$$C^*, x^* = \min_{x \in P_{\Pi}^-} \text{argmin} -Q_m((x^{i,j})_{i,j}). \quad (7)$$

375 Note that in practice $-Q_m$ cannot be convex. For a general cost $-Q_m$, the low dimensional prob-
 376 lem (7) can be approximated and solved using standard non-convex algorithms such as simulated
 377 annealing or branch and bound. Here, as Q_m is polynomial, the global solution on P_{Π}^- can be ap-
 378 proximated using the Lasserre hierarchy leading to a semidefinite programming (SDP) relaxation
 379 [27]. The complexity for solving the SDP relaxation is polynomial in the number of constraints
 380 defining P_{Π}^- [30], but exponential as a function of the relaxation level, thus only low levels can be
 381 used in practice. Upon solving the optimization problem (7), an optimal transport plan π^* can be
 382 derived from the solution $x^* \in V$, by solving the following convex problem (with standard convex
 383 optimization techniques [4]):

$$\pi^* = \text{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \|x^* - p_0(\pi)\|^2. \quad (8)$$

384 Note that π^* yields an approximation of the true optimal coupling for the GW_m problem, since we
 385 approximated P_{Π} with P_{Π}^- . To refine the cost and the optimal coupling, we run local optimization
 386 algorithm, such as Frank-Wolfe, with initial value π^* (see section 3.4).

387 3.3 Global optimization for a concave cost

388 In the specific case where $-Q_m$ is concave, we can solve the GW_m problem by leveraging that a
 389 solution is located at a vertex of the constraint polytope P_{Π}^- . This is the case for the **IGW** cost
 390 in all dimensions and for the **CGW** cost with parameter $1/2 \leq t < 1$ in dimension $d = 2$. In
 391 dimension $d = 3$ the concavity of the CGW cost depends on the size of the marginals μ, ν . If
 392 $\text{supp}(\mu) \subset \mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R)$ and $\text{supp}(\nu) \subset \mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R)$ for $R > 0$, we can choose $t \in \left[\frac{24R^2}{2+24R^2}, 1\right)$ to ensure
 393 concavity (see Supplementary C). Then, approximating GW_m can be done by computing the cost
 394 $-Q_m$ at all vertices of $P_{\Pi,k}^-$ using its V -representation, to solve (7). By construction the number of
 395 vertices of $P_{\Pi,k}^-$ is the number of iteration k plus the number of initial vertices (2^{d^2} when initialized

396 with Algorithm 6). In the concave case, problem (8) can be reformulated as a classical optimal
 397 transport problem:

$$\pi^* = \operatorname{argmax}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int \bar{g}(x, y) d\pi(x, y), \quad (9)$$

398 where $\bar{g} \in V$ is such that the supporting hyperplane of P_Π with normal \bar{g} contains $x^- = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in P_{\Pi, k}^-} -Q_m(x)$.
 399 At each iteration, if the vertex x_0 added to P_Π^- is optimal when searching in direction g_0 , we up-
 400 date $\bar{g} \leftarrow g_0$ and $x^- \leftarrow x_0$. Even if problem (9) may have several solutions, using a deterministic
 401 algorithm to solve it ensures $x^- = p_0(\pi^*)$. Algorithm 2 represents how to approximate the GW_m
 402 solution by adapting Algorithm 1 when the cost is concave. We can now estimate the complexity
 403 of this algorithm:

Algorithm 2 Main algorithm for GW_m in dimension d , concave cost

Require: $\epsilon > 0, \mu, \nu$.

- 1: Compute covariance matrix $\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu, \tilde{\Sigma}^\nu$
 - 2: Define: $f_{i,j} := (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d} \mapsto x^i y^j$
 - 3: Define bounding boxes $P_\Pi^+ := \{\}, P_\Pi^- := \{\}$, box cost $c^- = +\infty, c^+ = -\infty$ and optimal direction $\bar{g} = \emptyset$
 - 4: **Initialization of the bounding boxes:** $P_\Pi^-, P_\Pi^+, c^-, \bar{g}$ (Algorithm 7)
 - 5: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \min, \operatorname{argmin}_{P_\Pi^+}(-Q_m)$ done by enumeration
 - 6: **Updating bounding box until convergence**
 - 7: **while** $|c^+ - c^-| > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 8: Solve problem (5) given x^+ and compute optimal direction g
 - 9: Solve problem (4) and compute \hat{g}, g^*
 - 10: $P_\Pi^- \leftarrow \operatorname{conv}(P_\Pi^- \cup g^*)$
 - 11: $P_\Pi^+ \leftarrow P_\Pi^+ \cap H(g)$
 - 12: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \min, \operatorname{argmin}_{P_\Pi^+}(-Q_m)$ done by enumeration
 - 13: **if** $c^- < -Q_m(\hat{g})$ **then**
 - 14: $\bar{g} \leftarrow g$
 - 15: $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(\hat{g}_k)$
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: **end while**
 - 18: **Optimal coupling** π^* solving convex problem (9) given \bar{g}
 - 19: (Optional) π^*, c^- solving Frank-Wolfe(m, μ, ν, π^*)
 - 20: $\text{GW}^2 \leftarrow Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2c^-$
 - 21: **return** π^*, GW^2
-

404 **Theorem 3.** Assume that μ, ν are discrete, with at most N points. Under Assumption 1, Algorithm
 405 2 is a Fully Polynomial Time Approximation Scheme (FPTAS) for the GW_m problem. More
 406 precisely, Algorithm 2 enables to approximate $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2$ at a precision $\epsilon > 0$:

407 - with complexity $O\left(N^3 \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)^{2(d^2-1)(\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1)}\right)$,

408 - with memory of size $O\left(N^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)^{(d^2-1)(\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1)}\right)$,

409 where the implied constants only depend on d, m and R, λ specified in Assumption 1. In particular,
 410 they do not depend on the marginals μ, ν , as long as Assumption 1 holds.

411 Our evaluation of complexity Theorem 3 first results from estimating the bounding boxes size
 412 and applying Theorem 2, which states that the number of iterations needed to compute an ϵ -
 413 approximation of the GW_m cost only depends on ϵ and is independent of the sample size N . At
 414 iteration number k , the data needed to represent and efficiently update the bounding boxes has
 415 size $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$ and updating it has cost and memory size at most $O(k^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$. The complexity
 416 in N arises from solving an optimal transport problem, which happens once per iteration and has
 417 complexity $O(N^3)$. Note that we can alternatively compute an ϵ -approximation (in cost) of this
 418 problem using entropic regularization and the Sinkhorn algorithm, with complexity $O(N^2 \ln(N)\epsilon^{-3})$
 419 [33, Remark 4.6]. This has a significant practical advantage of enabling scaling the algorithm to
 420 large data size. But we note that in this case, the convergence rate is not known, as the noise due to
 421 Sinkhorn could impact the convergence of our algorithm. Interestingly, Algorithm 2 can be adapted
 422 to the 2-Gromov-Wasserstein cost (see Algorithm 5), with convergence rate described in Theorem 6 :
 423 Given μ, ν discrete measures with bounded support we can approximate $\text{GW}_2(\mu, \nu)^2$ at a precision
 424 $\epsilon > 0$ with complexity $O(\epsilon^{-2(d^2)\lfloor (d^2+1)/2 \rfloor + 1})$, and with memory of size $O(\epsilon^{-(d^2)\lfloor (d^2+1)/2 \rfloor + 1})$.
 425 For technical reasons, detailed in Supplementary B.2, the implied constant in this case depends on
 426 the marginals and their specific geometry. In contrast, the constant in the multilinear case is less
 427 constrained by the marginals as it only depends on R and λ (under assumption 1).

428 In practice, there is also no need to approximate the whole convex set P_Π to improve the
 429 convergence, but only regions with the lowest costs $-Q_m$. To do so, we use a different strategy
 430 than Kamenev [21] to choose the direction of the cuts. Instead of maximizing the gap between $P_{\Pi,k}^+$
 431 and $P_{\Pi,k}^-$ in the direction g_{k+1} as in (5), we set,

$$432 \quad g_{k+1} = \operatorname{argmax}_{g \in F(P_{\Pi,k}^-)} \left[\langle g, x^+ \rangle - \max_{h \in P_{\Pi,k}^-} \langle g, h \rangle \right], \quad (10)$$

432 with $x^+ = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in P_{\Pi,k}^+} -Q_m(x)$. In other words, we select the facet with the largest positive gap to
 433 x^+ , and use its normal vector as direction, ensuring that x^+ is removed from P_{Π}^+ when updated. This
 434 direction selection is thus a slight variation of (5), and similarly, the term $\max_{h \in P_{\Pi}^-} \langle g, h \rangle$ is known
 435 in the H -representation of P_{Π}^- . Some variants of the algorithm, that can be used to approximate
 436 solutions when the cost is concave are presented in Supplementary D, notably Algorithm 9 selecting
 437 the optimal direction based on (10). We are using it in practical applications.

438 Since the optimization of $-Q_m$ can be efficiently done at each iteration on both bounding
 439 boxes, the respective optimal costs c^+, c^- of $-Q_m$ on P_{Π}^+ and $P_{\Pi,k}^-$, can then be computed, yielding
 440 a certificate of optimality and convergence $|c^+ - c^-|$. This certificate enables one to upper and
 441 lower bound the global solution of GW_m , and to stop the algorithm when the bounds reach a given
 442 relative tolerance ϵ , i.e. if: $\frac{|c^+ - c^-|}{Q_m(\bar{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\bar{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2c^-} < \epsilon$. Figure 4 represents the certificate of optimality
 443 dynamics in a practical case. Note that c_- converges faster than c_+ in our simulations, specifically
 444 during the first iterations, as represented in Figure 3. Thus, a low number of iterations may yield
 445 a good approximation of the optimal cost even though the certificate is quite large.

446 3.4 Local optimization

447 Given an initial coupling π_0 we can apply the Frank-Wolfe algorithm [16] to compute a local
 448 optimum of the GW_m cost. In a continuous setting, we obtain Algorithm 3. Note that the cost for
 449 running it is alleviated by leveraging the low dimensional structure of the problem (see Corollary

450 2). Indeed, there is no need to compute the $2dn$ dimensional integral of the GW_m cost (with
451 $n \geq 2$), since the optimization problem only depends on the cross-covariance matrix Σ^{π_k} of the
452 coupling π_k , i.e. a $4d$ dimensional integral. Moreover, we can analytically compute the gradient of
453 the GW_m cost as the function $c_k : (x, y) \mapsto \langle x, \nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k})y \rangle$. Here the gradient $\nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \subset \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$
454 is reshaped as a $d \times d$ matrix. Note that we can write $c_k = \sum_{i,j} [\nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k})]_{i,j} f_{i,j}(x, y)$, with
455 the basis functions $f_{i,j}$ defined in Section 2.2 and Corollary 2. For the IGW and DGW costs,
456 $\nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k})$ respectively correspond, up to a positive constant, to Σ^{π_k} and the cofactor matrix of
457 Σ^{π_k} . Overall, these calculations rely on the fact that we can represent our problem in either the
458 infinite dimensional bounded convex set $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$, or the d^2 dimensional compact convex set $P_\Pi \subset V$.

Algorithm 3 Frank-Wolfe algorithm for GW_m

Require: $\pi_0 \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$, $\epsilon > 0$, cost polynomial Q_m (see Corollary 2)

- 1: Compute covariance matrices $\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu, \tilde{\Sigma}^\nu$
 - 2: **while** $k = 0$ or $\text{dist}(\pi_k, \pi_{k-1}) > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 3: Compute the cross covariance matrix Σ^{π_k} and the gradient $\nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k})$
 - 4: Define the cost function $c_k : (x, y) \mapsto \langle x, -\nabla Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_k})y \rangle$
 - 5: Compute $\hat{\pi}_{k+1} = \text{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})} c_k(x, y) d\pi(x, y)$ (optimal transport problem)
 - 6: $T, \tau \leftarrow \min, \text{argmin}_{\tau \in [0,1]} -Q_m((\tau \Sigma_{i,j}^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} + (1-\tau) \Sigma_{i,j}^{\pi_k})_{i,j})$ ($1-D$ polynomial problem for the
line search)
 - 7: $\pi_{k+1} \leftarrow \tau \hat{\pi}_{k+1} + (1-\tau) \pi_k$
 - 8: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
 - 9: **end while**
 - 10: $\text{GW}^2 = Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2T$
 - 11: **return** π_k, GW^2 or just T
-

459 Since Q_m is Lipschitz on P_Π , the objective value in Algorithm 3 converges towards the value
460 of a local stationary point of GW_m at a rate $O(\frac{1}{\sqrt{k}})$, with k the number of iterations [25]. The
461 complexity of each iteration corresponds to solving an optimal transport problem with the cost c_k
462 (step 5) and can be efficiently tackled with linear programming algorithms or approximated using
463 the Sinkhorn algorithm [8]. The line search step of the algorithm is a one dimensional polynomial
464 optimization over $[0, 1]$, which can be solved analytically for m of low enough degree, and can be
465 tackled in the general case using Newton methods and branch and bound. For example, we derived
466 analytical formulas and implemented them for the line search in the IGW case (in any dimension),
467 the DGW and CGW cases in dimension 2 or 3 (see Supplementary E).

468 4 Numerical experiments

469 We implemented the global optimization algorithm for concave cost as described in Section 3.3,
470 as well as the Frank-Wolfe algorithm of Section 3.4. We also provide an implementation of the
471 2-Gromov-Wasserstein distance.

472 Figure 2A represents the optimal costs and transport plans between a right-hand reference
473 shape (298 points) and a left-hand target shape. All the costs used are concave and have an
474 optimal transport map. We used the parameter $t = 0.501$ for the CGW cost. The color scheme of
475 the reference shape is transported using the GW_m optimal transport map. As expected, the IGW
476 and GW_2 costs do not capture the handedness (i.e. their chirality). Indeed, the optimal map is

Figure 2: Chiral shape comparison using the CGW distance. A) Transport of a reference right hand to a left hand, using the Classical, Inner and Chiral Gromov-Wasserstein optimal transport maps. Only the CGW distance yields a positive value between the two hands, capturing the change of handedness. B) Comparison of penicillamine conformations using the CGW distance. We compared either two penicillamine enantiomers after adding noise (with reflection), or two noisy versions of the same molecule (without reflection). Without reflection, the CGW distance and Root-Mean-Square Deviation (RMSD) are linearly correlated. On the right side, the boxplot represents CGW distance between conformations of the same handedness (without reflection) and different handedness (with reflection).

477 a reflection with respect to the horizontal axis and it yields a 0 cost. On the contrary the CGW
 478 distance is non-zero and its optimal map forces the transport between the pinky and the thumb.
 479 The evolution of c^+ and c^- , the bounds on the optimal cost, can be found in Figure 3. Note that
 480 the transported colormap for the CGW case is not continuous on the outline, which is typical for
 481 optimal transport between non-convex shapes [31].

482 Figure 2B represents comparison of penicillamine conformations. We are focusing on the two
 483 enantiomers: D- and L-penicillamine. On each structure, we add random Gaussian noise to sim-
 484 ulate small thermal fluctuations around a ground state [17]. We then compare conformations of
 485 molecules with same chirality (without reflection) or with different chirality (with reflection through
 486 the x-axis) using the CGW distance in 3D, with uniform weighting on each atom. We rescaled each
 487 molecule such that they are in a ball of radius 1, keeping the relative scale constant between each
 488 pair, and used a value of $t = 0.8$. We plotted the CGW distance between non-reflected conforma-
 489 tions (middle panel), as a function of the *Root-Mean-Square Deviation* (RMSD), which is a simple
 490 measure of how much the conformations differ. CGW and RMSD are linearly correlated, showing
 491 that CGW captures small deformations in shape as the RMSD does. Furthermore, we computed the
 492 CGW costs between molecules obtained without reflection and then with reflection and compared
 493 the two resulting distributions (right panel). The relatively larger CGW distances for molecules

494 with reflection suggests that CGW captures the chirality of the enantiomers (also note that this
495 experiment has been performed with only 60 iterations). As the molecule is small enough (9 atoms),
496 we have also optimized the objective by enumeration over all transport maps to confirm that our
497 algorithm converged to the global solution.

498 To study how our global optimization algorithm performs in practice with respect to the theoret-
499 ical bounds and complexity established earlier, we also generated experiments on standard Gaussian
500 distributions in 2 and 3D (see Figure 4). In particular, the complexity in number of vertices and
501 constraints of the bounding box, with respect to the number of iterations k was significantly less
502 than the upper bound derived in Theorem 3: In 2D, they are both linear while the upper bound is
503 quadratic (Figure 4A), enabling running several thousands of iterations without memory issues on a
504 standard laptop. Similarly in 3D, we found $O(k^3)$ while the upper bound is $O(k^4)$ (Figure 4B). Still,
505 computing GW_m distance for problems that require many iterations in our current implementation
506 reaches memory-time trade off limits when the bounding boxes have $\sim 10^5$ vertices or constraints.
507 This trade-off constitutes the main computational bottleneck, even when small number of points in
508 the shape allow for fast OT computation (e.g. in our penicillamine case study which has 9 points).
509 Second, even though Algorithm 3 has a relatively slow theoretical convergence rate (see Section 3.4),
510 our numerical experiments showed convergence in less than 50 iterations (Figure 5), suggesting it
511 is not the main limiting factor in globally solving the problem. Finally, as our algorithm shares
512 similarities with the one described in Ryner’s [35], we also compared their algorithm to ours. Note
513 that their superiority to generic non-linear global optimization algorithms was already established
514 in benchmarking [35]. Our algorithm performed similarly in the numerical experiments we ran, but
515 with some differences related to the number of iterations and the marginal size (see Figure 6 for
516 more details).

517 5 Conclusion and discussion

518 We introduced the multilinear Gromov-Wasserstein distance GW_m , as a powerful tool to compare
519 shapes up to transformations of a matrix Lie group G , provided the existence of a non-degenerate
520 multilinear form m associated with it (Propositions 3 and 4). This distance has theoretical proper-
521 ties that are relevant for practical use: it is robust to variations of the marginals in a quantifiable
522 way (Theorem 1), and the GW_m problem admits optimal correspondence maps, enabling shape reg-
523 istration and alignment. We have leveraged the low dimensional properties of the GW_m problem to
524 propose a local optimization scheme (Algorithm 3), as well as a *fully polynomial-time approximation*
525 of the global solution when the cost is concave, making the GW_m problem tractable. The **CGW**
526 distance is a specific example, relevant to biological and chemical applications as it captures the
527 chirality of objects by construction. For a parameter t large enough, the CGW_t cost is concave,
528 making the distance computable with our algorithm.

529 Upon implementing and testing our concave algorithm in dimensions 2 and 3, we confirmed that
530 the CGW distance captures change in shape chirality. While this algorithm is suitable to compare
531 2D shapes as is, some further optimization, that would for example take into account suitable data
532 structures, should enable running more iterations in dimension 3. We can also control the precision
533 of the algorithm at each iteration with a certificate of global optimality, that can potentially avoid
534 unnecessary computing. As highlighted in Section 3.3, our algorithm can run on large data, as
535 long as we can solve an optimal transport problem on it. In principle, this OT problem can be
536 approximated, using for example entropy-regularized optimal transport and the Sinkhorn algorithm
537 [8], low rank optimal transport [37]. As such approximations introduce noise in the cost, it would

538 be interesting to assess their impact on the algorithm stability. We are currently pursuing these
539 research directions.

540 **Data availability:** The implementation of our code in python can be found at this [repository](#),
541 which also includes extensive testing, the datasets and the numerical experiments of this paper.
542 The penicillamine structure originates from [PubChem](#) [24] with the compound CID: 4727.

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666 Notation

- 667 • \mathbb{R} the set of real numbers,
- 668 • d the dimension of the ambient space, typically $d = 2, 3$,
- 669 • $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, typically compact in practical applications, equipped with the canonical inner
670 product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$,
- 671 • $\|\cdot\|$ the 2-norm on \mathbb{R}^d ,
- 672 • $\|\cdot\|_F$ the matrix Frobenius norm,
- 673 • \det the determinant,
- 674 • For $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we will write $x = (x^1, \dots, x^d)$ its coordinates,
- 675 • $\mathbf{x} := (x_1, \dots, x_k) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^k$ is a family of elements of \mathbb{R}^d . It can be seen as an element of \mathbb{R}^{dk}
676 as well,
- 677 • $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$, space of probability measures on \mathcal{X} ,
- 678 • For $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$, we denote its second moment $\mathfrak{m}_2(\mu) := \int_{\mathcal{X}} \|x\|^2 d\mu$,
- 679 • $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ space of probability measures on \mathcal{X} with finite second moment,
- 680 • m multilinear n -form (or n tensor) over \mathbb{R}^d , $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0, 1\}$,
- 681 • G matrix Lie group over \mathbb{R} . Examples are $O(d), SO(d)$ the orthogonal and special orthogonal
682 groups, $SL(d)$ the special linear group, or $E(d), SE(d)$ Euclidean and special Euclidean group.
- 683 • $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ the set of couplings between $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$. $\Pi(\mu, \nu) \subset \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$,
- 684 • Given $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$, we define the product measures $\mu \times \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ and
685 $\mu^k \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}^k)$,
- 686 • Given a coupling $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$, we define $\pi^{\otimes k}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) := \prod_{i=1}^k \pi(x_i, y_i)$. In particular, $\pi^{\otimes k} \in$
687 $\Pi(\mu, \nu)^k$,
- 688 • Given a map $g : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, we define $g^{\times n} := (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathcal{X}^n \mapsto (g(x_1), \dots, g(x_n)) \in \mathcal{Y}^n$,
- 689 • Given $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ and $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, $f_*\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$ denotes the measure pushforward by f ,
- 690 • Given $\eta \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$, we define its covariance matrix $\tilde{\Sigma}^\eta = \int_{\mathcal{X}} xx^T d\eta(x)$,
- 691 • Given $\xi \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ we define its cross-covariance matrix $\Sigma^\xi = \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} xy^T d\xi(x, y)$,
- 692 • Given a symmetric matrix Σ , we define Spec its spectrum (the set of its eigenvalues),
- 693 • $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ refers to the expectation of a random variable,
- 694 • \mathcal{H}_2 refers to the Hausdorff distance between polytopes in a Euclidean space (using the 2-norm).

695 **Appendix A Proofs of Section 2**

696 **A.1 Proofs of Section 2.1**

697 **Proof of Lemma 1**

698 *Proof.* Let $(\mu, \nu) \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})^2$. We first show that $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) < \infty$. Take the coupling $\pi_0 = \mu \times \nu$.
699 We have:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 &\leq \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi_0^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} m(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mu^n - 2 \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} m(\mathbf{x}) d\mu^n \int_{\mathcal{Y}^n} m(\mathbf{y}) d\nu^n + \int_{\mathcal{Y}^n} m(\mathbf{y})^2 d\nu^n < +\infty, \end{aligned}$$

700 since the last term is polynomial function of the two first moments of μ, ν . In fact, if $m(\mathbf{x}) =$
701 $\sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \in [1, d]^n} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n}$ is the expansion of the multilinear form on the canonical basis,
702 then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} m(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mu^n &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} x_1^{i_1} x_1^{j_1} \dots x_n^{i_n} x_n^{j_n} d\mu^n \\ &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{\mathcal{X}} x_1^{i_1} x_1^{j_1} d\mu \dots \int_{\mathcal{X}} x_n^{i_n} x_n^{j_n} d\mu \\ &\stackrel{\text{(Cauchy-Schwarz)}}{\leq} \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{\mathcal{X}} \|x_1\|^2 d\mu \dots \int_{\mathcal{X}} \|x_n\|^2 d\mu < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

703 Now, GW_m is clearly non-negative and symmetric; and $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \mu) = 0$ since

$$\int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X})^n} |m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y})|^2 d(\text{id}, \text{id})_{\#} \mu^{\otimes n} = 0.$$

704 Finally, let's prove that the triangle inequality holds. Using the Gluing Lemma [11, Theorem 1.1.10],
705 given $\mu, \gamma, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ and transport plans in $\pi_{\mu, \gamma} \in \Pi(\mu, \gamma)$, $\pi_{\gamma, \nu} \in \Pi(\gamma, \nu)$, there exists $\pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}^3)$,
706 with marginals $\pi_{\mu, \gamma}$ and $\pi_{\gamma, \nu}$ when projecting on the first and third copy of \mathcal{X} respectively. Here
707 we choose $\pi_{\mu, \gamma}, \pi_{\gamma, \nu}$ optimal solutions of $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \gamma), \text{GW}_m(\gamma, \nu)$ respectively and define $\pi_{\mu, \nu} =$

708 $\int_{\mathcal{X}} \pi(\cdot, dx, \cdot)$, then $\pi_{\mu, \nu} \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$. Now:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) &\leq \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^2)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{z}))^2 d\pi_{\mu, \nu}^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^3)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{z}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^3)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}) - (m(\mathbf{z}) - m(\mathbf{y})))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\stackrel{\text{(Minkowski)}}{\leq} \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^3)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^3)^n} (m(\mathbf{z}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^2)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi_{\mu, \gamma}^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\int_{(\mathcal{X}^2)^n} (m(\mathbf{z}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi_{\gamma, \nu}^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \text{GW}_m(\mu, \gamma) + \text{GW}_m(\gamma, \nu).
\end{aligned}$$

709 Altogether, GW_m is a pseudo-distance on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$. □

710 **Proof of Proposition 1**

711 *Proof.* Let's fix $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$. Without loss of generality we can suppose that μ, ν are centered; in
712 this case, let's study $\inf_{t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d} C(\pi, x, y)$. Expanding the term in the integral, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\inf_{t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d} C(\pi, x, y) &= \inf_{t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{i}_n(t)) - m(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{i}_n(u))]^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\
&= C(\pi, 0, 0) + \inf_{t, u \in \mathbb{R}^d} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{i}_n(t)) - m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{i}_n(u)) + m(\mathbf{y})]^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\
&\quad + 2 \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{i}_n(t)) - m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{i}_n(u)) + m(\mathbf{y})][m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y})] d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}).
\end{aligned}$$

713 The first integral is non-negative. Let's prove that the second integral is actually 0. We can expand
714 $m(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{i}_n(t)) - m(\mathbf{x})$ into a sum involving t in at least one entry of m , at entry i let's say, such that
715 we write $m(\dots, t_i, \dots)$. Now integrating over the i -th copy of $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$ we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} m(\dots, t_i, \dots) m(\mathbf{x}) d\pi(x_i, y_i) &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} m(\dots, t_i, \dots) m(x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n) d\mu(x_i) \\
&= m(\dots, t_i, \dots) m(x_1, \dots, \int_{\mathcal{X}} x_i d\mu(x_i), \dots, x_n) \\
&= m(\dots, t_i, \dots) m(x_1, \dots, 0_i, \dots, x_n) = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

716 We used here the multilinearity and that μ is centered. Similarly,

$$\int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} m(\dots, t_i, \dots) m(\mathbf{y}) d\pi(x_i, y_i) = 0.$$

717 Finally, we have $\inf_{t,u \in \mathbb{R}^d} C(\pi, t, u) = C(\pi, 0, 0)$, so the claim holds. \square

718 **Proof of Proposition 2**

719 *Proof.* Given $\alpha > 0$ and $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$, we define

$$\begin{aligned} C(\pi, \alpha) &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\alpha \mathbf{y})]^2 d\pi^{\otimes n} \\ &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} [m(\mathbf{x}) - \alpha^n m(\mathbf{y})]^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} m(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mu^n + \alpha^{2n} \int_{\mathcal{Y}^n} m(\mathbf{y})^2 d\nu^n - 2\alpha^n \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} m(\mathbf{x})m(\mathbf{y}) d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}). \end{aligned}$$

720 Now $\text{GW}_m(\mu, U_\alpha \# \nu) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} C(\pi, \alpha)$. Given a solution π^* minimizing $C(\pi, \alpha)$, π^* equivalently
721 solves

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -2 \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} m(\mathbf{x})m(\mathbf{y}) d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \quad \text{and} \quad \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} C(\pi, 1).$$

722 In particular, we deduce that if π^* solves the $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ problem then $(\text{id}_{\mathcal{X}}, U_\alpha \circ \text{id}_{\mathcal{Y}}) \# \pi^*$ solves the
723 $\text{GW}_m(\mu, U_\alpha \# \nu)$ problem. Applying the same argument the other way around, we also deduce a one
724 to one correspondence between the solutions of $\text{GW}_m(\mu, U_\alpha \# \nu)$ and $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$. \square

725 **Proof of Lemma 2**

726 It is a direct corollary of the following lemma:

727 **Lemma 4.** *Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and m be a non-degenerate n -form on \mathbb{R}^d . Assume that there exists
728 $x_1, \dots, x_d \in A$ a basis of \mathbb{R}^d . Then,*

$$\{T : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d, m \circ T^{\times n} = m\} \subset GL(d),$$

729 *and the unique linear extension of T to \mathbb{R}^d , \tilde{T} , verifies $m \circ \tilde{T}^{\times n} = m$.*

730 *Proof of Lemma 4.* Without loss of generality, we assume that m is non-degenerate at slot 1. Using
731 the multilinearity of m , we can write:

$$\forall y, y_2, \dots, y_n \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad m(y, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \langle y, f(y_2, \dots, y_n) \rangle.$$

732 Here $f : (\mathbb{R}^d)^{n-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ with its coordinates being multilinear $n-1$ forms.

733 We note $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, \dots, z_{n-1}) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^{n-1}$. First, let's prove that there exists $(\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_d) \in (A^{n-1})^d$
734 such that $(f(\mathbf{z}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{z}_d))$ is a basis of \mathbb{R}^d . Let's assume this is not true, then there exists $v \in \mathbb{R}^d$,
735 such that for all $y_1, \dots, y_{n-1} \in A$, $m(v, y_1, \dots, y_{n-1}) = \langle v, f(y_1, \dots, y_{n-1}) \rangle = 0$. Since a basis of \mathbb{R}^d
736 is contained in A , we deduce by linearity, that $m(v, y_1, \dots, y_{n-1}) = 0$ for all $y_1, \dots, y_{n-1} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. This
737 contradicts the non-degeneracy assumption. From now on, we fix the vectors $\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_d \in A^{n-1}$
738 such that $(f(\mathbf{z}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{z}_d))$ is a basis of \mathbb{R}^d .

739 Using our assumption, let's choose $(x) = (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in A^d$ a basis of \mathbb{R}^d . Let's define $e_i =$
740 $f(\mathbf{z}_i) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for $1 \leq i \leq d$. Then $(e) := (e_1, \dots, e_d)$ is a basis of \mathbb{R}^d , as well. Now, for $1 \leq i, j \leq d$,

$$\langle x_i, e_j \rangle = m(x_i, \mathbf{z}_j) = m(T(x_i), T^{\times n-1}(\mathbf{z}_j)) = \langle T(x_i), f(T^{\times n-1}(\mathbf{z}_j)) \rangle. \quad (11)$$

741 Let's define the $d \times d$ matrix M , as $M_{i,j} = \langle x_i, e_j \rangle$. Since (e) and (x) are bases, M is invertible.
 742 Let's rewrite $f(T^{\times n-1}(\mathbf{z}_i)) = g_i$. From (11), we also have $M_{i,j} = \langle T(x_i), g_j \rangle$. Since M is invertible,
 743 (g) and $(T(x))$ are basis of \mathbb{R}^d as well. In particular, $\text{span}(T(A)) = \mathbb{R}^d$. Moreover, T is linear since
 744 (11) implies,

$$\forall y \in A \text{ with coordinates } (\alpha) \text{ on } (x), \forall 1 \leq i \leq d, \quad \langle T(y), g_i \rangle = \left\langle \sum_i \alpha_i T(x_i), g_i \right\rangle.$$

745 Finally, T is linear and surjective, thus invertible. Now, using the linearity of T and m , \tilde{T} , the
 746 linear extension of T to \mathbb{R}^d , is uniquely defined and we have $m \circ \tilde{T}^{\times n} = m$. \square

747 Proof of Proposition 3

748 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be compact and $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ have a density with respect to the Lebesgue
 749 measure. Note that this implies that \mathcal{X} has non-zero Lebesgue measure. We just need to prove
 750 that for $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$:

$$\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0 \implies \exists g \in G, \mu = g_{\#}\nu.$$

751 We suppose that $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0$. Under the compactness and density assumption, Lemma 3 proves
 752 the existence of an optimal Monge map $T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$. In other words, an optimal solution π^* of the
 753 $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ problem can be written $\pi^* = (id, T)_{\#}\mu$; and $\nu = T_{\#}\mu$. Accordingly,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 \\ &= \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X})^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X})^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d(\pi^*)^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(T^{\times n}(\mathbf{x})))^2 d\mu^n(\mathbf{x}). \end{aligned}$$

754 It remains to show that $T \in GL(d)$.

755 Without loss of generality, we can suppose that m is non-degenerate at slot 1. Using the
 756 multilinearity of m , we can write:

$$\forall x, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad m(x, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \langle x, f(x_2, \dots, x_n) \rangle,$$

757 with $f : (\mathbb{R}^d)^{n-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ whose components are multilinear $(n-1)$ -forms. We define

$$B_1 := \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_d \in (\mathcal{X})^{n-1}, (f(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_d)) \text{ is a basis of } \mathbb{R}^d\},$$

758 and we have

$$B_1^c = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_d \in (\mathcal{X})^{n-1}, \det(f(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_d)) = 0\}.$$

759 But, $\det(f(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_d)) = 0$ is a polynomial equation, since f has polynomial coordinates. Now
 760 the non-degeneracy assumption implies that B_1 is non-empty, thus $B_1^c \subsetneq \mathbb{R}^{d^2(n-1)}$. As the set of
 761 solutions of a polynomial equation $\text{Leb}(B_1^c) = 0$ and $\mu^{d(n-1)}(B_1) = 1$. Similarly, the following set
 762 $B_2 := \{x_1, \dots, x_d \in (\mathcal{X})^d, (x_1, \dots, x_d) \text{ is a basis of } \mathbb{R}^d\}$ has measure one.

763 Let $A \subset \mathcal{X}$ with $\mu(A) > 0$. By modifying A on a set of μ -measure zero, we can assume that
 764 $m \circ T^{\times n} = m$ on all of A . Observe that $\mu^{dn}((B_2 \times B_1) \cap A^{dn}) = \mu(A) > 0$. By construction, A and
 765 m satisfy the assumptions of Lemma 4. Hence, there exists $T \in GL(d) \cap G$, such that $\mu = T_{\#}\nu$. In
 766 particular, $T \in G$. \square

767 **Proof of Proposition 4**

768 *Proof.* Let μ, ν be two point clouds of size k in \mathbb{R}^d : $\mu = 1/k \sum_1^k \delta_{x_i}$ and $\nu = 1/k \sum_1^k \delta_{y_i}$, with
 769 $x_i \neq x_j$ and $y_i \neq y_j$ if $i \neq j$. Let's prove:

$$\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0 \implies \exists g \in G, \mu = g\sharp\nu.$$

770 We suppose that $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu) = 0$. We write π^* the optimal transport plan as a $k \times k$ matrix, where
 771 $\pi_{i,j}^*$ represent the mass transported from x_i to y_j . The non-zero volume implies that $k \geq d$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 \\ &= \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d)^n} (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \sum_{(i_l, j_l) \in A(\pi^*)} (m(x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_n}) - m(y_{j_1}, \dots, y_{j_n})) \prod_{l=1}^n \pi_{i_l, j_l}^*, \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

772 where $A(\pi^*)$ is the set of indices (i, j) where π^* has non-zero entries. Let's now prove that for an
 773 index i , there exists only one index j such that $\pi_{i,j}^* \neq 0$. Let's assume this is not the case. Without
 774 loss of generality we can assume $i = 1$ and that $\pi_{1,1}^* > 0, \pi_{1,2}^* > 0$. Now,

$$\forall (i_2, j_2), \dots, (i_n, j_n) \in A(\pi^*), \quad m(x_1, x_{i_2}, \dots, x_{i_n}) = m(y_1, y_{j_2}, \dots, y_{j_n}) = m(y_2, y_{j_2}, \dots, y_{j_n}).$$

775 In particular, the non-zero volume assumption and the fact that π^* is a coupling assures us that
 776 we can find $(i_1, \alpha_1), \dots, (i_d, \alpha_d) \in A(\pi^*)$, such that $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d$ forms a basis of \mathbb{R}^d . But then:

$$\forall 1 \leq l_1, \dots, l_n \leq d, \quad m(y_1 - y_2, y_{\alpha_{l_1}}, \dots, y_{\alpha_{l_n}}) = 0.$$

777 By linearity, we conclude that $m(y_1 - y_2, \cdot, \dots, \cdot) = 0$ as a $n - 1$ multilinear form, with $y_1 - y_2 \neq 0$,
 778 which violates the non-degeneracy condition of m .

779 A consequence of this result is that π^* is an extremal point of the constraint polytope $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$
 780 (a rescaled version of the Birkhoff polytope in our case). Such an extremal point is a scaled
 781 permutation matrix. Thus, there exists a map $T : \text{supp}(\mu) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ such that $\mu = T\sharp\nu$ and T
 782 preserves the multilinear form m i.e. $m \circ T^{\times n} = m$. Finally we use the non-zero volume assumption
 783 and apply Lemma 4 to conclude that $T \in GL(d) \cap G$. In particular, $T \in G$. \square

784 **Proof of Corollary 1**

785 *Proof.* This result holds since

$$G_{\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle} := \{T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle = \langle T(\cdot), T(\cdot) \rangle\} = O(d),$$

786 and

$$G_{\det} := \{T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d, \det = \det \circ T^{\times d}\} = SL(d).$$

787 \square

788 A.2 Proofs of Section 2.2

789 Proof of Proposition 5

790 *Proof of Proposition 5.* Let $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $\mu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$. Let's first rewrite the
791 $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ problem:

$$\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 = \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} m(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mu^n + \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} m(\mathbf{y})^2 d\nu^n + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -T_\pi,$$

792 with

$$T_\pi := \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} m(\mathbf{x})m(\mathbf{y})d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}). \quad (13)$$

793 Let $m(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \in [1, d]^n} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n}$, the expansion of the multilinear form on the canon-
794 ical basis. We can compute the first two terms as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} m(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mu^n &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{\mathcal{X}^n} x_1^{i_1} x_1^{j_1} \dots x_n^{i_n} x_n^{j_n} d\mu^n \\ &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{\mathcal{X}} x_1^{i_1} x_1^{j_1} d\mu \dots \int_{\mathcal{X}} x_n^{i_n} x_n^{j_n} d\mu \\ &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \tilde{\Sigma}_{i_1, j_1}^\mu \dots \tilde{\Sigma}_{i_n, j_n}^\mu =: Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu). \end{aligned}$$

795 Note that this term is non-negative. Since we can choose a marginal μ to get any symmetric PSD
796 matrix, the polynomial Q_m is non-negative over all symmetric PSD matrices. Q_m has d^2 variables
797 and a degree at most n . Rewriting T_π and integrating recursively, we obtain similarly:

$$\begin{aligned} T_\pi &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} x_1^{i_1} y_1^{j_1} \dots x_n^{i_n} y_n^{j_n} d\pi^{\otimes n}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} \Sigma_{i_1, j_1}^\pi \dots \Sigma_{i_n, j_n}^\pi = Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) = Q_m(\tilde{p}_0(\pi)). \end{aligned}$$

798 Let's prove that \tilde{p}_0 is continuous. Let π_n converge to π with respect to W_2 in $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$. We define
799 the functions $f_{i,j} : (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto x^i y^j \in \mathbb{R}$. Note that for $\eta \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$, $\tilde{p}_0(\eta)_{i,j} = \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} f_{i,j} d\eta$.
800 If we note $\mathbf{x} = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$, then we have $|f_{i,j}(x, y)| \leq 2(\|x\|^2 + \|y\|^2) = 2\|(x, y)\|^2$. We conclude
801 from Theorem 4 that $\tilde{p}_0(\pi_n) \rightarrow \tilde{p}_0(\pi)$ in \mathbb{R}^{d^2} . Since \tilde{p}_0 is linear and $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ is convex, \tilde{P}_Π is convex
802 as well. Since \tilde{p}_0 is continuous and $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ is compact, \tilde{P}_Π is compact. Finally,

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\tilde{p}_0(\pi)_{i,j}^{i,j}) = \inf_{x \in \tilde{p}_0(\Pi(\mu, \nu))} -Q_m((x^{i,j})_{i,j}) = \inf_{x \in \tilde{P}_\Pi} -Q_m((x^{i,j})_{i,j}),$$

803 where $(x^{i,j})$ is the coordinate in the $(f_{i,j})$ basis. □

804 **Proof of Corollary 2**

805 *Proof.* This proof is based on the previous one. We assume that \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} are compact, so is $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$. Let
 806 $f_{i,j} : (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto x^i y^j \in \mathbb{R}$ for $1 \leq i, j \leq d$. Since \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} are full dimensional, $(f_{i,j})$ is a linearly
 807 independent family. Let's use the L^2 inner product on $V = \text{span}(f_{i,j}) \subset \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ as $\langle f, g \rangle =$
 808 $\int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} fg$. We can now choose $(e_i)_{1 \leq i \leq d^2}$ an orthonormal basis of V and define $p_0 : L^2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}) \rightarrow V$
 809 the orthogonal projection over V . Now, as $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}) \cap L^2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$ is dense in $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$, we can
 810 naturally extend p_0 to $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$, such that

$$\forall v \in V, \pi \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}), \quad \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} v d\pi = \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} \sum_i \langle v, e_i \rangle e_i d\pi = \sum_i \langle v, e_i \rangle \langle p_0(\pi), e_i \rangle = \langle v, p_0(\pi) \rangle.$$

811 Let $\mathcal{R}_f : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ the representation of the family $(f_{i,j})_{i,j}$ in the basis $(e_{i,j})_{i,j}$, then \mathcal{R}_f is linear
 812 invertible. Now $\tilde{p}_0 = \mathcal{R}_f \circ p_0$. Thus, p_0 is also continuous, and P_Π is compact and convex. \square

813 **Proof of Example 2**

814 *Proof.* Now let's apply the results of Proposition 5 to the 3 costs defined earlier. We compute the
 815 cost linearization, useful for numerical schemes (like the Frank-Wolfe algorithm as in Section 3.4).
 816 Let's extend the term T_π as defined in (13).

817 1. **IGW.**

$$\begin{aligned} T_\pi &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \langle y_1, y_2 \rangle d\pi^{\otimes 2} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} \left\langle x_1, \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} x_2 y_2^T d\pi(x_2, y_2) y_1 \right\rangle d\pi(x_1, y_1) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} \langle x_1, \Sigma^\pi y_1 \rangle d\pi(x_1, y_1). \end{aligned}$$

818 We can also express this term under this form:

$$\begin{aligned} T_\pi &= \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq d} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} x_1^i x_2^i y_1^j y_2^j d\pi^{\otimes 2} \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq d} (\Sigma_{i,j}^\pi)^2 \\ &= \|\Sigma^\pi\|_F^2, \end{aligned}$$

819 with $\|\cdot\|_F$ the Frobenius norm. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IGW}(\mu, \nu)^2 &= \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle - \langle y_1, y_2 \rangle|^2 d\pi^{\otimes 2} \\ &= \|\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu\|_F^2 + \|\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu\|_F^2 + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} \langle x, \Sigma^\pi y \rangle d\pi \\ &= \|\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu\|_F^2 + \|\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu\|_F^2 + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -\|\Sigma^\pi\|_F^2. \end{aligned}$$

820 2. **DGW**. We rewrite T_π as:

$$\begin{aligned}
T_\pi &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} \det(x_1, \dots, x_d) \det(y_1, \dots, y_d) d\pi^{\otimes d} \\
&= \sum_{\sigma_x, \sigma_y \in S(d)} \operatorname{sgn}(\sigma_x) \operatorname{sgn}(\sigma_y) \\
&\quad \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} (x_1)_{\sigma_x(1)} (y_1)_{\sigma_y(1)} \cdots (x_d)_{\sigma_x(d)} (y_d)_{\sigma_y(d)} d\pi^{\otimes d} \\
&= \sum_{\sigma_x, \sigma_y \in S(d)} \operatorname{sgn}(\sigma_x) \operatorname{sgn}(\sigma_y) \Sigma_{\sigma_x(1), \sigma_y(1)}^\pi \cdots \Sigma_{\sigma_x(d), \sigma_y(d)}^\pi \\
&= \sum_{\sigma_x, \sigma_y \in S(d)} \operatorname{sgn}(\sigma_y) \Sigma_{1, \sigma_y(1)}^\pi \cdots \Sigma_{d, \sigma_y(d)}^\pi \\
&= d! \det(\Sigma^\pi).
\end{aligned}$$

821 Using the Laplace expansion of the determinant along all the rows of Σ^π , we can express the
822 determinant in terms of Δ , the matrix of first minors of Σ^π ;

$$\begin{aligned}
T_\pi &= d! \det(\Sigma^\pi) \\
&= (d-1)! \sum_{i,j} \Sigma_{i,j}^\pi (-1)^{i+j} \Delta_{i,j} \\
&= (d-1)! \int \langle x, \operatorname{com}(\Sigma^\pi) y \rangle d\pi,
\end{aligned}$$

823 with $\operatorname{com}(M)$ the matrix of cofactors of M . Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{DGW}(\mu, \nu)^2 &= \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} |\det(\mathbf{x}) - \det(\mathbf{y})|^2 d\pi^{\otimes d} \\
&= d! \det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + d! \det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2(d-1)! \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} - \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^d} \langle x, \operatorname{com}(\Sigma^\pi) y \rangle d\pi \quad (14) \\
&= d! \left[\det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + \det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} - \det(\Sigma^\pi) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

824 3. **CGW**. We get by linearity:

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{CGW}(t, \mu, \nu)^2 &= A + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} - \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} \langle x, [t\Sigma^\pi + (t-1)(d-1)! \operatorname{com}(\Sigma^\pi)] y \rangle d\pi \\
&= A + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -t \|\Sigma^\pi\|_F^2 - (1-t)d! \det(\Sigma^\pi), \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

825 with

$$A = t[\|\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu\|_F^2 + \|\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu\|_F^2] + (1-t)d![\det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + \det(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu)].$$

826

□

827 A.3 Low dimensional structure of the 2-Gromov-Wasserstein

828 We go over the low dimensional structure of the classical Gromov-Wasserstein problem, similar
 829 to Corollary 2. Assume $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ are bounded. Here we suppose that the marginals $(\mu, \nu) \in$
 830 $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}) \times \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$ are centered. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GW}_2(\mu, \nu)^2 &= \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} (||x_1 - x_2||^2 - ||y_1 - y_2||^2)^2 d\pi^{\otimes 2} \\ &= \int ||x_1 - x_2||^4 d\mu^2 + \int ||y_1 - y_2||^4 d\nu^2 - 4 \int ||x||^2 ||y||^2 d\mu \times \nu \\ &\quad + \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -4 \int ||x||^2 ||y||^2 d\pi - 8 \int \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \langle y_1, y_2 \rangle d\pi^{\otimes 2} \end{aligned}$$

831 Here only the last line depends on the coupling. We can then derive a low dimensional representation
 832 as in Corollary 2 with $V = \text{span}(g, (f_{i,j})_{i,j})$, $g : x, y \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto ||x||_2^2 ||y||_2^2$ and $f_{i,j} : x, y \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto$
 833 $x^i y^j$. We equip V with the $L^2(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})$ inner product and we define p_0 the extension to $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$
 834 of the orthogonal projection on V similarly to Corollary 2. p_0 is still continuous as a consequence
 835 of Theorem 4, and $P_\Pi = p_0(\Pi(\mu, \nu))$ is still convex bounded. Now, the term depending on the
 836 coupling π is equal to:

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -4 \int g d\pi - 8 ||\Sigma^\pi||_F^2 = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -4 \langle g, p_0(\pi) \rangle - 8 \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq d} \langle f_{i,j}, p_0(\pi) \rangle^2 =: Q(p_0(\pi))$$

837 Thus, the cost only depends polynomially on the projection of the coupling on V a vector space of
 838 dimension $d^2 + 1$. Note that the cost is concave in π , and we can use a variant of our Algorithm 1
 839 to compute its global optimal value. We can also run the Frank-Wolfe Algorithm 3 to compute a
 840 local solution, with the cost becoming:

$$c_k : (x, y) \mapsto 8 \langle x, \Sigma^{\pi_k} y \rangle + 4 ||x||^2 ||y||^2 = 4g(x, y) + 8 \sum_{i,j} \Sigma_{i,j}^{\pi_k} f_{i,j}(x, y).$$

841 A.4 Proofs of Section 2.3

842 Auxiliary results

843 Let (\mathcal{X}, D) be a Polish space and $p \in [1, +\infty)$. Let $\mathcal{P}_p(\mathcal{X})$ be the set of probability distributions on
 844 \mathcal{X} with finite p -th moment. We define the p -Wasserstein distance on $\mathcal{P}_p(\mathcal{X})$ as

$$W_p(\mu, \nu) = \left(\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int D(x, y)^p d\pi \right)^{1/p}.$$

845 We quote the following characterization of the W_p topology. We denote $\xrightarrow{*}$ the weak-* convergence.

846 **Theorem 4** (Definition 6.6 and Theorem 6.7 of [44]). *Let (\mathcal{X}, D) be a complete separable metric*
 847 *space, and $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}, \mu \in \mathcal{P}_p(\mathcal{X})$. The following are equivalent:*

- 848 1. $W_p(\mu_n, \mu) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.
- 849 2. $\mu_n \xrightarrow{*} \mu$ in duality with $C_b(\mathcal{X})$, and for some $x_0 \in \mathcal{X}$, $\int D^p(x_0, x) d\mu_n(x) \rightarrow \int D^p(x_0, x) d\mu(x)$.

850 3. $\mu_n \xrightarrow{*} \mu$ in duality with the continuous functions with growth of degree p :

$$C_p(\mathcal{X}) := \{\varphi \in C(\mathcal{X}) : \exists x_0 \in \mathcal{X}, \exists a > 0, |\varphi(x)| \leq a(D^p(x, x_0) + 1)\}.$$

851 We will be using the following technical lemma.

852 **Lemma 5.** *Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$. Then*

$$W_2^2(\mu \times \mu, \nu \times \nu) \leq 2W_2^2(\mu, \nu).$$

853 *Proof.* Let π^* be an optimal coupling between μ and ν . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \int d_{\mathcal{X}^2}^2((x, x'), (y, y')) d\pi^*(x, y) \times d\pi^*(x', y') &= \int (d_{\mathcal{X}}^2(x, y) + d_{\mathcal{X}}^2(x', y')) d\pi^*(x, y) \times d\pi^*(x', y') \\ &= 2W_2^2(\mu, \nu). \end{aligned}$$

854 The left-hand side is an upper bound for $W_2^2(\mu \times \mu, \nu \times \nu)$ because the (x, x') -marginal of $d\pi^*(x, y) \times$
855 $d\pi^*(x', y')$ is equal to $d\mu(x) \times d\mu(x')$, and similarly for ν . \square

856 We shall also use the following result, which says that the entire set of couplings is stable with
857 respect to perturbations of the marginals.

858 **Lemma 6** (Theorem 1 of [3]). *Let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be complete, separable metric spaces, and $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in$
859 $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$. Then for every measure $\pi_1 \in \Pi(\mu_1, \nu_1)$ there exists a measure $\pi_2 \in$
860 $\Pi(\mu_2, \nu_2)$ such that $W_2(\pi_1, \pi_2) \leq W_2(\mu_1, \mu_2) + W_2(\nu_1, \nu_2)$.*

861 Proof of Proposition 6

862 *Proof.* Let's denote $|\cdot|$ the two norm. To show existence of minimizers, we first observe that, given
863 $\mu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$, $\nu \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$ and a coupling $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$,

$$|\Sigma^\pi|^2 = \sum_{i,j=1}^d \left| \int x^i y^j d\pi \right|^2 \leq \sum_{i,j=1}^d \left(\int |x^i y^j| d\pi \right)^2 \leq \sum_{i,j} \int |x^i|^2 d\pi \int |y^j|^2 d\pi = \int |x|^2 d\mu \int |y|^2 d\nu < +\infty.$$

864 Note that we also have from Proposition 5:

$$0 \leq \int (m(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{y}))^2 d\pi^{\otimes n} = Q(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) - 2Q(\Sigma^\pi),$$

865 so that

$$2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q(\Sigma^\pi) \geq -Q(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) - Q(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) > -\infty.$$

866 Let π_j be a sequence in $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ satisfying $\mathcal{C}(\pi_j) \searrow \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathcal{C}(\pi)$; by Theorem 4 it holds that
867 $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ is precompact with respect to the W_2 topology on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$, meaning that we can extract
868 a convergent subsequence (not relabeled) such that $W_2(\pi_j, \pi^*) \rightarrow 0$ for some limit point π^* . Fur-
869 thermore, $\pi^* \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$, as can be seen by integrating π^* against test functions depending only on
870 one coordinate. Thanks to Theorem 4, the function $\pi \mapsto \Sigma^\pi$ is continuous, thus $\pi \mapsto \mathcal{C}(\pi) = Q(\Sigma^\pi)$
871 is also continuous, and it holds that $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}(\pi_j) = \mathcal{C}(\pi^*)$. Hence, π^* is a minimizer.

872 Now, let $\pi_k^* \in \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu_k, \nu_k)} \mathcal{C}(\pi_k)$. Since μ_k and ν_k are each convergent sequences with
 873 respect to W_2 , by Theorem 4 it holds that the sequence π_k^* is precompact with respect to the W_2
 874 topology on $\mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})$; so as before, we can extract a convergent subsequence (not relabeled) such
 875 that $W_2(\pi_k^*, \pi^*) \rightarrow 0$ for some limit point π^* ; furthermore, $\pi^* \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$.

876 We deduce that $\mathcal{C}(\pi_k^*) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(\pi^*)$; it remains to show that $\pi^* \in \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathcal{C}(\pi)$. To this end,
 877 let $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$ be arbitrary. In view of Lemma 6, we can produce a sequence $\pi_k \in \Pi(\mu_k, \nu_k)$ such
 878 that $W_2(\pi_k, \pi) \rightarrow 0$. Note that this means that $\mathcal{C}(\pi_k) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(\pi)$, again by Theorem 4. Of course,
 879 $\mathcal{C}(\pi_k^*) \leq \mathcal{C}(\pi_k)$ since π_k^* is a minimizer. Therefore, (passing to the same subsequence as for π_k^*) we
 880 have

$$\mathcal{C}(\pi^*) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}(\pi_k^*) \leq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}(\pi_k) = \mathcal{C}(\pi).$$

881 Since $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$ was arbitrary, this shows that π^* is a minimizer as desired. \square

882 Proof of Theorem 1

883 Let's first prove this proposition:

884 **Proposition 7.** *Let $\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $\tilde{p}_0 : \pi \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}) \mapsto \Sigma^\pi \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ and $\tilde{P}_\Pi^{\mu, \nu} := \tilde{p}_0(\Pi(\mu, \nu))$. Let
 885 $\mu, \mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\nu, \nu_0 \in \mathcal{P}_2(\mathcal{Y})$. We assume $\mathfrak{m}_2(\mu_0), \mathfrak{m}_2(\nu_0), \mathfrak{m}_2(\mu), \mathfrak{m}_2(\nu) \leq \alpha$ for some $\alpha > 1$.
 886 Then the Hausdorff distance \mathcal{H}_2 (as defined in (6)) satisfies:*

$$\mathcal{H}_2(\tilde{P}_\Pi^{\mu_0, \nu_0}, \tilde{P}_\Pi^{\mu, \nu}) \leq 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\alpha}(W_2(\mu_0, \mu) + W_2(\nu_0, \nu)). \quad (16)$$

887 *Proof of Proposition 7.* Let $f_{i,j} : \mathbf{z} = (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \mapsto x^i y^j \in \mathbb{R}$ the product of the i -th and
 888 j -th component and $\pi_1 \in \Pi(\mu_0, \nu_0), \pi_2 \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$. Let $\Theta^* \in \Pi(\pi_1, \pi_2) \subset \mathcal{P}_2((\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2)$ be the
 889 optimal coupling for the W_2 distance between π_1 and π_2 . Then for $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2 \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$, let's rewrite
 890 $\sum_{i,j} |f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_1) - f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_2)|$ as:

$$\sum_{i,j} |x_1^i y_1^j - x_2^i y_2^j| \leq \sum_{i,j} |x_1^i y_1^j - x_1^i y_2^j| + |x_1^i y_2^j - x_2^i y_2^j| \leq \sum_{i,j} |x_1^i| |y_1^j - y_2^j| + |y_2^j| |x_1^i - x_2^i|.$$

891 Now :

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Sigma^{\pi_1} - \Sigma^{\pi_2}\|_F^2 &\leq \sum_{i,j} \left| \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} f_{i,j} d\pi_1 - \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}} f_{i,j} d\pi_2 \right|^2 = \sum_{i,j} \left| \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_1) - f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_2) d\Theta^* \right|^2 \\ &\leq \sum_{i,j} \left| \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_1) - f_{i,j}(\mathbf{z}_2)| d\Theta^* \right|^2 = \sum_{i,j} \left| \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |x_1^i| |y_1^j - y_2^j| + |y_2^j| |x_1^i - x_2^i| d\Theta^* \right|^2 \\ &\leq 2 \sum_{i,j} \left| \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |x_1^i| |y_1^j - y_2^j| d\Theta^* \right|^2 + \left| \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |y_2^j| |x_1^i - x_2^i| d\Theta^* \right|^2 \\ &\stackrel{\text{(Cauchy-Schwarz)}}{\leq} 2 \sum_{i,j} \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |x_1^i|^2 d\Theta^* \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |y_1^j - y_2^j|^2 d\Theta^* + \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |y_2^j|^2 d\Theta^* \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} |x_1^i - x_2^i|^2 d\Theta^* \\ &\leq 2 \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} \|\mathbf{z}\|^2 d\Theta^* \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^2} \|\mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2\|^2 d\Theta^* \\ &\leq 8\alpha W_2(\pi_1, \pi_2)^2, \end{aligned}$$

892 where in the last inequality, we have used the fact that $\int \|\mathbf{z}\|_2^2 d\Theta^* = \mathbf{m}_2(\pi_1) + \mathbf{m}_2(\pi_2) = \mathbf{m}_2(\mu_0) +$
 893 $\mathbf{m}_2(\nu_0) + \mathbf{m}_2(\mu) + \mathbf{m}_2(\nu) \leq 4\alpha$.

894 Finally, for $x \in \tilde{P}_{\Pi}^{\mu_0, \nu_0}$, we can write $x = \Sigma^{\pi_1}$ for $\pi_1 \in \Pi(\mu_0, \nu_0)$. Applying Lemma 6 we can
 895 find $\pi_2 \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$ such that $W_2(\pi_1, \pi_2) \leq W_2(\mu, \nu) + W_2(\mu_0, \nu_0)$. If we denote $y = \Sigma^{\pi_2} \in \tilde{P}_{\Pi}^{\mu, \nu}$, we
 896 have

$$\|x - y\| \leq 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\alpha}(W_2(\mu_0, \mu) + W_2(\nu_0, \nu)).$$

897 Similarly, for $\tilde{y} \in \tilde{P}_{\Pi}^{\mu, \nu}$, we can find $\tilde{x} \in \tilde{P}_{\Pi}^{\mu_0, \nu_0}$ such that

$$\|\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}\| \leq 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\alpha}(W_2(\mu_0, \mu) + W_2(\nu_0, \nu)),$$

898 and (16) holds. □

899 *Proof of Theorem 1.* This proof follows from Proposition 7. Given $\pi_1 \in \Pi(\mu_0, \nu_0), \pi_2 \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$ we
 900 have:

$$\|\Sigma^{\pi_1}\|_F^2 = \sum_{i,j} \left(\int x^i y^j d\pi_1 \right)^2 \leq \sum_{i,j} \int |x^i|^2 d\pi_1 \int |y^j|^2 d\pi_1 = \mathbf{m}_2(\mu_0)\mathbf{m}_2(\nu_0) \leq \alpha^2.$$

901 Similarly, $\|\Sigma^{\pi_2}\|_F^2 \leq \alpha^2$. The Lipschitz constant of the polynomial Q_m on the ball $\mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(\alpha)$ can
 902 be upper bounded by $c_1\alpha^{n-1}$, with c_1 only depending on the coefficients of Q_m . As an example
 903 we can take c_1 to be the ℓ^1 norm of the coefficients of Q_m . Thus, $|Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_1}) - Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_2})| \leq$
 904 $2\sqrt{2}c_1\alpha^{n-1/2}(W_2(\mu_0, \mu) + W_2(\nu_0, \nu))$. Similarly,

$$\|\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}\|_F^2 = \sum_{i,j} \left(\int x^i x^j d\mu \right)^2 \leq \sum_{i,j} \int |x^i|^2 d\mu \int |x^j|^2 d\mu = \left(\int \|x\|^2 d\mu \right)^2 \leq \alpha^2.$$

905 We can also apply the same computations as in the proof of Proposition 7 to get:

$$\|\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu} - \tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu_0}\|_F \leq \sqrt{2} W_2(\mu_0, \mu) \sqrt{\int \|x\|^2 d\mu + \int \|y\|^2 d\mu_0} \leq 2\sqrt{\alpha}W_2(\mu_0, \mu).$$

906 Thus, $|Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}) - Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu_0})| \leq 2c_1\alpha^{n-1/2}W_2(\mu_0, \mu)$. But we have

$$|\text{GW}_m(\mu_0, \nu_0)^2 - \text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2| \leq 2|Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_1}) - Q_m(\Sigma^{\pi_2})| + |Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu}) - Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\mu_0})| + |Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\nu}) - Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^{\nu_0})|,$$

907 and we deduce (3). □

908 We now cover the example given in Remark after Theorem 1. Under the assumption that μ, ν
 909 have finite q moments for q high enough ($q > 4$ when $d \leq 2$ or $q > 2d/(d-2)$ otherwise), [15,
 910 Theorem 1] gives us :

$$\mathbb{E}[W_2(\hat{\mu}_k, \mu)] \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[W_2^2(\hat{\mu}_k, \mu)]} \leq c_0\phi_k,$$

911 with $\phi_k = k^{-\frac{1}{\max(d,4)}} \ln(k)^{\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{1}_{\{d=4\}}}$ and c_0 depending on the q -th moment of μ and the dimension
 912 only. We refer to the reader to [45] for the convergence of the empirical distance in different settings.
 913 Using the result of Theorem 1, we conclude:

$$\mathbb{E}[|\text{GW}_m(\hat{\mu}_k, \hat{\nu}_k)^2 - \text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2|] \leq c\alpha^{n-1/2}\phi_k.$$

914 Here the constant c only depends on the q -th moment of the marginals, the multilinear form m and
 915 the dimension d .

916 **Proof of Lemma 3**

917 *Proof.* As shown previously $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)^2 = Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2 \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} -Q_m(\Sigma^\pi)$. We now
 918 focus on the last term. Let's expand the multilinear form $m(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \in [1, d]^n} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n}$,
 919 and rewrite:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^n} \sum_{\substack{(i_1, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_1, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n} y_1^{j_1} \dots y_n^{j_n} d\pi^{\otimes n} \\ &= \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})} \sum_{i_1, j_1} x_1^{i_1} M_{i_1, j_1}^\pi y_1^{j_1} d\pi(x_1, y_1), \end{aligned}$$

920 with

$$M_{i_1, j_1}^\pi = \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})^{n-1}} \sum_{\substack{(i_2, \dots, i_n) \\ (j_2, \dots, j_n)}} \alpha_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \alpha_{j_1, \dots, j_n} x_2^{i_2} \dots x_n^{i_n} y_2^{j_2} \dots y_n^{j_n} d\pi^{\otimes n-1}.$$

921 Thus, we can write

$$Q_m(\Sigma^\pi) = \int_{(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y})} \langle x_1, M^\pi y_1 \rangle d\pi(x_1, y_1).$$

922 Let's define the cost

$$C_\pi(x, y) = \langle x, M^\pi y \rangle.$$

923 This representation of the GW_m cost and our compactness assumption enable us to apply the proof
 924 of [12, Theorem 3.2] to yield the existence of the Monge Map. For the sake of completeness we
 925 include the adapted proof and used results below.

926 Let π^* be an optimal coupling for the $\text{GW}_m(\mu, \nu)$ problem. It also solves

$$\inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int \langle x, M^{\pi^*} y \rangle d\pi(x, y).$$

927 Using a singular value decomposition, we write $M^{\pi^*} = O_1^T \Sigma_0 O_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ with $(O_1, O_2) \in O_d(\mathbb{R})^2$
 928 orthogonal matrices and $\Sigma_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{d^2}$ diagonal with non-negative entries. The cost C_{π^*} then becomes

$$C_{\pi^*}(x, y) = -\langle O_2^T \Sigma_0 O_1 x, y \rangle = -\langle \Sigma_0 O_1 x, O_2 y \rangle.$$

929 Using Lemma 7, the problem becomes an optimal transportation problem between $\mu' := O_{1\#} \mu$
 930 and $\nu' := O_{2\#} \nu$. Up to permutation of the rows and columns of O_1 and O_2 , we can assume that the
 931 non-zero eigenvalues of Σ_0 are $\sigma_1 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_h > 0$, with $h := \text{rank}(M^*) \leq d$. The problem therefore
 932 becomes $\min_{\tilde{\pi}} \langle c_{\Sigma_0}, \tilde{\pi} \rangle$ for $\tilde{\pi} \in \Pi(\mu', \nu')$, where $c_{\Sigma_0}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) = -\sum_{i=1}^h \sigma_i \tilde{x}_i \tilde{y}_i =: \tilde{c}(p(\tilde{x}), p(\tilde{y}))$, and p is
 933 the orthogonal projection on \mathbb{R}^h .

934 The existence of an optimal map T_0 between μ' and ν' follows from the application of Theorem 5
 935 for $E := E_0 := \mathbb{R}^d = \mathbb{R}^h \times \mathbb{R}^{d-h} =: B_0 \times F$ and $\varphi := p$. Indeed, B_0 and F are complete Riemannian
 936 manifolds, the cost \tilde{c} satisfies the twist condition on $B_0 \times B_0$, $p_{\#} \mu' \ll \text{Leb}_h$, and $\mu'_u \ll \text{Leb}_{d-h}$
 937 as a conditional probability for a.e. u . One can then induce an optimal map between μ and ν by
 938 composing with O_1 and O_2^T (Lemma 7).
 939

940 Now, one has that $c_{\Sigma_0}(x, y) = -\langle \tilde{\Sigma}_0 x, y \rangle$, where $\tilde{\Sigma}_0 = \text{diag}(\sigma_i)_{1 \leq i \leq h}$. As $p_{\sharp} \mu'$ has a density,
 941 we can apply Lemma 8 stated below with $(\psi_1, \psi_2) = (\tilde{\Sigma}_0, \text{id})$ to obtain the existence of a unique
 942 optimal transport plan between $p_{\sharp} \mu'$ and $p_{\sharp} \nu'$ for the cost c_{Σ_0} .
 943 □

944 **Theorem 5** (Theorem 2.4 of [12], truncated). *Let E_0 be a measurable space and B_0 and F be*
 945 *complete Riemannian manifolds. Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(E_0)$ be two probability measures with compact sup-*
 946 *port. Assume that there exists a set $E \subset E_0$ such that $\mu(E) = 1$ and that there exists a measurable*
 947 *map $\Phi : E \rightarrow B_0 \times F$ that is injective and whose inverse, when restricted to its image, is mea-*
 948 *surable as well. Let p_B and p_F denote the projections of $B_0 \times F$ on B_0 and F respectively, and*
 949 *let $\varphi := p_B \circ \Phi : E \rightarrow B_0$. Let $c : E_0 \times E_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and suppose that there exists a cost function*
 950 *$\tilde{c} : B_0 \times B_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the twist condition:*

$$\forall x_0 \in B_0, \quad y \mapsto \nabla_x \tilde{c}(x_0, y) \in T_{x_0} B_0 \text{ is injective,}$$

951 *such that*

$$c(x, y) = \tilde{c}(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in E_0 \times E_0.$$

952 *Assume that $\varphi_{\sharp} \mu \ll \text{vol}_{B_0}$. Let $\mu' := \Phi_{\sharp} \mu$ and $\nu' := \Phi_{\sharp} \nu$. Suppose that there exists a disintegration*
 953 *$(\mu'_u)_{u \in B_0}$ of μ' by p_B such that for $\varphi_{\sharp} \mu$ -almost every u , $\mu'_u \ll \text{vol}_F$.*
 954 *Then there exists an optimal map $T : E \rightarrow E$ between μ and ν for the cost c .*

955 **Lemma 7** (Lemma 3.3 of [12]). *Let E, F be Polish spaces, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(E)$ and let $\psi_1, \psi_2 : E \rightarrow F$ be*
 956 *homeomorphisms. Let $\tilde{c} : F \times F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and consider the cost $c(x, y) = \tilde{c}(\psi_1(x), \psi_2(y))$. Then a map*
 957 *is optimal for the cost c between μ and ν if and only if it is of the form $\psi_2^{-1} \circ T \circ \psi_1$ with $T : F \times F$*
 958 *optimal for the cost \tilde{c} between $\psi_{1\sharp} \mu$ and $\psi_{2\sharp} \nu$.*

959 **Lemma 8** (Lemma 3.4 of [12]). *Let $h \geq 1$ and $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^h)$ with compact supports and such that*
 960 *$\mu \ll \text{Leb}_h$. Consider the cost $c(x, y) = -\langle \psi_1(x), \psi_2(y) \rangle$ where $\psi_1, \psi_2 : \mathbb{R}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^h$ are diffeomor-*
 961 *phisms. Then there exists a unique optimal transport plan between μ and ν for the cost c , and it is*
 962 *induced by a map $t : \mathbb{R}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^h$ of the form $t = \psi_2^{-1} \circ \nabla f \circ \psi_1$, with $f : \mathbb{R}^h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ convex.*

963 Appendix B Proof of Section 3

964 B.1 Proof of Section 3.1

965 Auxiliary results

966 We first need to estimate the volume of the projection P_{Π} :

967 **Lemma 9** (Dimension of P_{Π}). *Under the Assumption 1, there exists $r_0 > 0$ depending only on*
 968 *λ, d, R such that $\mathcal{B}_0^V(r_0) \subset P_{\Pi}$. Thus, $\dim(P_{\Pi}) = d^2$. Moreover, letting $r_R = \int_{\mathcal{B}_0^d(R)} x_1^2 dx_1 \dots dx_d >$
 969 *0, then $P_{\Pi} \subset \mathcal{B}_0^V(\frac{R^2}{r_R})$.**

970 *Proof of Lemma 9.* Let $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R)$. For the first assertion, we can assume that μ, ν are centered
 971 without loss of generality. Let's first note that $\Sigma^{\mu \otimes \nu} = p_0(\mu \otimes \nu) = 0$, so $0 \in P_{\Pi}$. We will prove
 972 that there exist $r_0 > 0$ such that for all $v \in V$ unit vector, $\max_{y \in P_{\Pi}} \langle v, y \rangle \geq r_0$. That implies
 973 $\mathcal{B}_0^V(r_0) \subset P_{\Pi}$, which we are proving now by contradiction. Let's assume that $\mathcal{B}_0^V(r_0) \not\subset P_{\Pi}$ and

974 define $x_0 = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in \partial V} \|x\|_2$. Then $\|x_0\|_2 < r_0$ and x_0 is a critical point of the squared norm on
 975 ∂V , which has gradient $2x_0$. By convexity of P_Π , x_0 is included in the supporting hyperplane of
 976 P_Π with normal $\frac{x_0}{\|x_0\|_2}$, i.e.

$$\forall x \in P_\Pi, \langle x, \frac{x_0}{\|x_0\|_2} \rangle \leq \|x_0\|_2 < r_0.$$

977 Given a vector $e \in \mathbb{R}^d$, we define the function $f_e^\mathcal{X} : x \in \mathcal{X} \mapsto \langle x, e \rangle \in \mathbb{R}$. Let $f_{1,1}$ be a unit vector
 978 of V (in the L^2 norm), we can write $f_{1,1} = \frac{1}{r_R} f_{e_1}^\mathcal{X} f_{\tilde{e}_1}^\mathcal{X}$ with $(e_1, \tilde{e}_1) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X}$ unit vectors. Indeed,
 979 $\|f_{e_1}^\mathcal{X} f_{\tilde{e}_1}^\mathcal{X}\| = \|f_{e_1}^\mathcal{X}\|^2 = \int_{\mathbb{B}_0^{d-1}(R)} x_1^2 dx_1 \dots dx_d = r_R$. Let's extend e_1, \tilde{e}_1 to $(e), (\tilde{e})$ orthogonal bases of
 980 \mathbb{R}^d and we define $f_{i,j} = \frac{1}{r_R} f_{e_i}^\mathcal{X} f_{\tilde{e}_j}^\mathcal{X}$. By construction $(f_{i,j})$ is an orthonormal basis of V . Let's denote
 981 x^i the coordinate of x in (e) and y^i the coordinate of y in (\tilde{e}) . We disintegrate both marginals
 982 μ, ν by projecting onto the first coordinate as follows: $\mu(x^1, \dots, x^d) = \mu_1(x^1) \mu_{x^1}(x^2, \dots, x^d)$, and
 983 $\nu(y^1, \dots, y^d) = \nu^1(y^1) \nu_{y^1}(y^2, \dots, y^d)$. Here, μ_1, ν_1 are the projections over the first coordinate. By
 984 construction μ_1, ν_1 are centered with non-zero variance as, for $g = id$ or $g = |\cdot|^2$:

$$\int_{[-R,R]} g(x_1) d\mu_1(x_1) = \int_{[-R,R]} g(x_1) \left(\int_{[-R,R]^{d-1}} \mu_{x^1}(x^2, \dots, x^d) \right) d\mu_1(x_1) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x_1) d\mu,$$

985 since μ_{x^1} is almost surely a probability distribution μ_1 . In particular, the variance of μ_1, ν_1 is lower
 986 bounded by the smallest eigenvalue of $\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu$ and by λ . Let π_1 be the optimal transport plan
 987 for the 1-d 2-Wasserstein distance between μ_1 and ν_1 :

$$\pi_1 = \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu_1, \nu_1)} \int \|x - y\|^2 d\pi = \operatorname{argmax}_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu_1, \nu_1)} \int xy d\pi.$$

988 We now define the following coupling $\tilde{\pi}(x^1, \dots, x^d, y^1, \dots, y^d) = \pi_1(x^1, y^1) \mu_{x^1} \otimes \nu_{y^1}(x^2, \dots, x^d, y^2, \dots, y^d)$.
 989 This is indeed a coupling since :

$$\begin{aligned} \int \tilde{\pi}(dx^1, \dots, dx^d, y^1, \dots, y^d) &= \nu_{y^1}(y^2, \dots, y^d) \int \left(\int \mu_{x^1}(dx^2, \dots, dx^d) \right) \pi_1(dx^1, y^1) \\ &= \nu_{y^1}(y^2, \dots, y^d) \int \pi_1(dx^1, y^1) \\ &= \nu_{y^1}(y^2, \dots, y^d) \nu_1(y^1) = \nu(y^1, \dots, y^d). \end{aligned}$$

990 And similarly for μ . Now:

$$r_R \left\langle p_0(\tilde{\pi}), \frac{f_{1,1}}{r_R} \right\rangle = \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X}} x^1 y^1 d\tilde{\pi} = \int \left(\int \mu_{x^1} \otimes \nu_{y^1}(x^2, \dots, x^d, y^2, \dots, y^d) \right) x^1 y^1 d\pi_1(x^1, y^1) = \int xy d\pi_1(x, y).$$

991 We know that μ_1, ν_1 are centered, have a diameter at most R and have respective variances $s_1, s_2 \geq$
 992 λ . Let $A_{R,\lambda}$ the set of all centered probability distributions over $[-R, R]$ with variance larger than
 993 λ . Let's prove a more general result:

$$\exists r_2 > 0, \quad \forall \eta, \xi \in \mathcal{P}([-R, R]) \text{ centered with } \tilde{\Sigma}^\eta, \tilde{\Sigma}^\xi \geq \lambda, \quad \sup_{\pi \in \Pi(\eta, \xi)} \int xy d\pi(x, y) \geq r_2.$$

994 Indeed, suppose this is not true. Since $[-R, R]$ is compact, so are $A_{R,\lambda}, \mathcal{P}([-R, R]^2)$ and $\bigcup_{\eta, \xi \in A_{R,\lambda}} \Pi(\eta, \xi)$.
 995 Then, there exists $\eta, \xi \in A_{R,\lambda}$ such that $\max_{\pi \in \Pi(\eta, \xi)} \int xy d\pi = 0$. Let $\hat{\pi}$ denote the optimal coupling

996 of that problem. In dimension 1, $\hat{\pi}$ is unique [36, Theorem 2.9], and fully characterized as follows
 997 [36, Lemma 2.8]:

$$\forall (x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in \text{supp}(\pi_1), \quad x_1 < x_2 \implies y_1 \leq y_2.$$

998 Since η, ξ are centered with non-zero variance, they have both at least two distinct elements in their
 999 respective support, thus $\hat{\pi} \neq \eta \otimes \xi$ and $\int xy d\hat{\pi} > \int xy d\eta \otimes \xi = 0$. Finally, we can take $r_0 = r_2/r_R$
 1000 to prove the first assertion.

1001 We now prove that $P_\Pi \subset \mathcal{B}_0^V(\frac{R^2}{r_R})$. Let μ, ν follow Assumption 1, they may not be centered. We
 1002 use the notations defined above, and denote x^1 the first coordinate of x in the basis (e) , y^1 the first
 1003 coordinate of y in the basis (\tilde{e}) . For $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$:

$$r_R \left| \left\langle p_0(\pi^*), \frac{f_{1,1}}{r_R} \right\rangle \right| = \left| \int_{\mathcal{X}^2} x^1 y^1 d\pi_1(x, y) \right| \leq \sqrt{\int_{\mathcal{X}^2} (x^1)^2 d\pi_1(x, y)} \sqrt{\int_{\mathcal{X}^2} (y^1)^2 d\pi_1(x, y)} \leq R^2.$$

1004 since $\int_{\mathcal{X}^2} (x^1)^2 d\pi \leq \int_{\mathcal{X}} \|x\|^2 d\mu$. To conclude, for any unit vector $v \in V$, we have

$$|\langle p_0(\pi^*), v \rangle| \leq \frac{R^2}{r_R},$$

1005 thus $p_0(\pi^*) \in \mathcal{B}_0^V(\frac{R^2}{r_R})$. □

1006 In this proposition, we describe how to initialize the bounding boxes to ensure a minimal size
 1007 to P_Π^- .

1008 **Proposition 8** (Bounding box initialization). *Let's suppose that there exists $r_0, r_1 > 0$ such that*
 1009 $\mathcal{B}_0^V(r_0) \subset P_\Pi \subset \mathcal{B}_0^V(r_1)$. *Algorithm 6 constructs bounding boxes $P_{\Pi,0}^- \subset P_\Pi \subset P_{\Pi,0}^+$ with the*
 1010 *following properties: there exists $x_0 \in V$ and there exists $r_2 > 0$ only depending on d, r_0, r_1 such*
 1011 *that:*

$$\mathcal{B}_{x_0}^V(r_2) \subset P_{\Pi,0}^- \quad \text{and} \quad P_{\Pi,0}^+ \subset \mathcal{B}_{x_0}^V(2dr_1).$$

1012 *Proof of Proposition 8.* For each iteration $k > 1$, let's define $v^+ = \max(|\langle g_k^* - \hat{g}_{+1}, e_k \rangle|, |\langle g_{-k}^* -$
 1013 $\hat{g}_{+1}, -e_k \rangle|)$. The assumption $\mathcal{B}_0^V(r_0) \subset P_\Pi$ implies $v^+ \geq \frac{r_0}{2}$. If we write vol_k the k dimensional
 1014 unsigned volume created by the convex hull of a set of points, then $\text{vol}_k(S_k^2) = \frac{v}{2} \text{vol}_{k-1}(S_{k-1}^2)$
 1015 by construction. Note that $\text{vol}_1(S_1^2) \geq r_0$. Finally, $S_{d^2}^2$ has a d^2 dimensional volume of at least
 1016 $r_0^{d^2}/(4^{d^2-1})$. By construction $S_{d^2}^+ = P_{\Pi,0}^+$ is a rectangular bounding box of radius at most dr_1 . Let's
 1017 now prove that there exists $x_0 \in \mathcal{B}_0^V(r_1)$ and $r_2 > 0$ such that $\mathcal{B}_{x_0}^V(r_2) \subset S_{d^2}^2 \subset P_{\Pi,0}^-$.
 1018 Let

$$A = \left\{ (x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1}) \in \mathcal{B}_0^V(r_1), \text{vol}_{d^2}(x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1}) \geq \frac{r_0^{d^2}}{4^{d^2-1}} \right\}.$$

1019 This is a non-empty compact set, and if we note (p_1, \dots, p_{d^2+1}) the vertices of $S_{d^2}^2$, then $(p_1, \dots, p_{d^2+1}) \in$
 1020 A . Given $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1}) \in V^{d^2+1}$, we define:

$$B^-(\mathbf{x}) = \max(\|r\|_2, (r, x) \in [0, 2r_1] \times \mathcal{B}_0^V(r_1) \text{ and } \mathcal{B}_x^V(r_0) \subset \text{conv}(x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1})).$$

1021 Here conv stands for the convex hull of the points. Then B^- is a continuous function and $B^-(A)$ is
 1022 also a non-empty compact set. Let's assume that $\inf B^-(A) = 0$. Then there exists $(x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1}) \in$
 1023 $\mathcal{B}_0^V(dr_1)$, with an empty interior and satisfying $\text{vol}_{d^2}(x_1, \dots, x_{d^2+1}) \geq \frac{r_0^{d^2}}{4^{d^2-1}}$, which is absurd.
 1024 Finally, we take $r_2 = \inf B^-(A) > 0$ depending only on r_0, d and r_1 . □

1025 **Proof of Theorem 2**

1026 *Proof.* Let \mathcal{H}_2 be the Hausdorff distance for polytopes in V as defined in (6). This result is a direct
 1027 corollary of Lemma 4.9 of [26], which states that, if there exists $r_0, r_1 > 0$ and $x_0 \in V$ such that
 1028 $\mathcal{B}_{x_0}^V(r_0) \subset P_{\Pi,0}^-$ and $P_{\Pi,0}^+ \subset \mathcal{B}_{x_0}(r_1)$, then

$$\mathcal{H}_2(P_{\Pi,k}^+, P_{\Pi,k}^-) \leq c_0 k^{-1/(d^2-1)}, \text{ for } k \geq d^2 + 1,$$

1029 with c_0 depending on r_0, r_1 and d only. Now, Proposition 8 and Lemma 9 enable us to select
 1030 suitable values for r_0, r_1 as a function of d, R and λ only. \square

1031 **B.2 Proofs of Section 3.3**

1032 **Proof of Theorem 3**

1033 *Proof.* We now go over the complexity of our algorithm. Let's fix $\epsilon > 0$ and $d \geq 2$ a fixed number
 1034 (typically $d = 2$ or 3). If the marginals μ, ν are discrete with at most N points in the marginals,
 1035 solving an optimal transport problem has complexity $O(N^3)$ [33, Section 3.7]. From Theorem 2
 1036 there exists c_0 depending on d, R and λ only such that:

$$\mathcal{H}_2(P_{\Pi,k}^+, P_{\Pi,k}^-) \leq c_0 k^{-1/(d^2-1)}, \text{ for } k \geq d^2 + 1.$$

1037 But $P_{\Pi,0}^- \subset P_{\Pi} \subset P_{\Pi,0}^+ \subset \mathcal{B}_0^V(4dR^2/r_R)$ and Q_m is β -Lipschitz for some $\beta > 0$ on $\mathcal{B}_0^V(4dR^2/r_R)$.
 1038 Thus,

$$\left| \min_{x \in P_{\Pi,k}^-} -Q_m(x) - \min_{y \in P_{\Pi,k}^+} -Q_m(y) \right| \leq \beta \mathcal{H}_2(P_{\Pi,k}^+, P_{\Pi,k}^-).$$

1039 This implies that the number k_f of iterations in Algorithm 2 to reach a precision ϵ in cost is at most
 1040 $k_f = O\left(\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)^{(d^2-1)}\right)$, where the implied constant does not depend on the marginals, only on $d, R,$
 1041 β and λ . Let's study the complexity of our algorithm. We can initialize the bounding boxes with
 1042 a finite number of cuts (each time an optimal transport problem is solved) as seen in Algorithm 7.
 1043 At each iteration k , we solve one optimal transport problem (line 9) and add a vertex to P_{Π}^- and
 1044 a constraint to P_{Π}^+ , thus their number of respective vertices/constraints is $O(k)$. A consequence
 1045 of the Upper Bound Theorem is that the number of faces (of any dimension) of a d^2 dimensional
 1046 polytope with k vertices can be upper bounded by $2^{d^2+1} \binom{k}{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor} \leq 2^{d^2+1} k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor}$ [28, Section 5.5].
 1047 Hence, the number of respective vertices/constraints in P_{Π}^+ and P_{Π}^- has order $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.

1048 At each iteration of our algorithm:

- 1049 • The optimal direction for the new cut (line 8) is selected by solving (5). This can be done by
 1050 enumerating the pairs constraints/vertices in P_{Π}^-/P_{Π}^+ and has a complexity $O(k^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.
- 1051 • An optimal transport problem with marginals μ, ν is solved (line 9), with complexity $O(N^3)$.
- 1052 • The V -representation of P_{Π}^- and H -representation of P_{Π}^+ are updated, with complexity $O(1)$.
- 1053 • The H -representation of P_{Π}^- and V -representation of P_{Π}^+ are updated, with complexity
 1054 $O(k^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$ (See next paragraph).

1055 • A new optimal cost for $-Q_m$ on P_{Π}^-, P_{Π}^+ is computed. This can be done by enumerating
 1056 vertices of the polytopes, i.e. with complexity $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.

1057 We now elaborate on how the V -representation of P_{Π}^+ is updated. We are using the data
 1058 structure described in [35, Appendix A3], and use their notation. Let E be the set of extreme
 1059 points of P_{Π}^+ (its V -representation), it has size $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$. Let A be the set of constraints of P_{Π}^+
 1060 (its H -representation), it has size $O(k)$. We also need an adjacency matrix D between the vertices
 1061 of P_{Π}^+ . It represents the faces of the polytope of dimension $d^2 - 1$ and has thus size $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$. We
 1062 define a binary matrix B linking vertices and constraints: if vertex i satisfies constraint j $B_{i,j} = 1$,
 1063 else $B_{i,j} = 0$. B has size $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$. When a new constraint is added:

- 1064 • A is updated with complexity $O(1)$.
- 1065 • Infeasible extreme points are computed using the matrix product $A.E$, with complexity
 1066 $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$.
- 1067 • Their adjacent vertices are selected, with complexity $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.
- 1068 • Each adjacency leads to compute at most one new vertex with complexity $O(1)$.
- 1069 • E is updated with complexity $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.
- 1070 • B is updated with complexity $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$.
- 1071 • Finally, D has to be updated, which can be done by selecting pairs of newly created vertices
 1072 solving the same $d^2 - 1$ constraints. In other words, each pair of rows newly added to B is
 1073 compared, with a total complexity of $O(k^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$.

1074 The H -representation of P_{Π}^- is updated in a similar manner, using a dual polytope P_D^- . Adding
 1075 a point to P_{Π}^- is equivalent to adding a constraint to P_D^- , which is handled as previously de-
 1076 scribed. Going back and forth between the primal and dual representation consists in enumerating
 1077 constraints or vertices, and has complexity at most $O(k^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor})$.

1078 Finally, the complexity of running iteration k is $O(N^3 k^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$ and the final complexity is
 1079 $O(N^3 k_f^{2\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 2})$. In terms of memory, the largest set is the matrix B and the transport plan needs
 1080 to be stored, needing a space of size $O(N^2 + k_f^{\lfloor d^2/2 \rfloor + 1})$. □

1081 **Complexity for solving the 2-Gromov-Wasserstein distance**

1082 As we have seen in Section A.3, the classical Gromov-Wasserstein 2 distance $\text{GW}(\mu, \nu)$ can be
 1083 computed by solving $\inf_{x \in P_\Pi} -Q(x)$, with P_Π a compact convex set of dimension at least $d^2 + 1$
 1084 and $-Q$ a concave polynomial with $d^2 + 1$ variables. Contrary to the Assumption 1, there is no
 1085 simple assumption enabling us to lower bound the volume of P_Π (in order to apply Proposition 8
 1086 and the proof of Theorem 2). As an example, if μ, ν are supported on centered unit spheres of \mathbb{R}^d ,
 1087 $\int g d\pi = 1$ for all $\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)$ and P_Π has zero volume. To remediate this problem, one can first
 1088 compute the dimension of P_Π by iteratively computing supporting hyperplanes and extreme points
 1089 of P_Π in orthogonal directions, as represented in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Computing dimension of P_Π

```

1:  $g_0 \leftarrow p_0(\mu \otimes \nu)$ 
2:  $\tilde{V}, \hat{V} \leftarrow \emptyset, \emptyset$ 
3: for  $k \in [1, d^2 + 1]$  do
4:   Choose  $e_k$  unit vector of  $V$  orthogonal to  $\tilde{V}$  and  $\hat{V}$ 
5:   Solve problem (4) and compute  $\hat{g}_\pm, g_\pm^*$  with direction  $g = \pm e_k$ 
6:    $\hat{V} \leftarrow \hat{V} \cup \{g_+^* - g_0, g_-^* - g_0\}$ 
7:   if  $g_\pm^* = -g_\mp^*$  ( $g$  is orthogonal to  $P_\Pi$ ) then
8:      $\tilde{V} \leftarrow \tilde{V} \cup \{e_k\}$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: return  $(\hat{e})$  orthonormal basis of  $\hat{V}$ 

```

1090 This algorithm outputs the base of a vector space $\hat{V} \subset V$ such that $P_\Pi \subset \hat{V}$ and P_Π has non-
 1091 zero volume in this space. We can then run an algorithm similar to Algorithm 2 on the space \hat{V} .
 1092 The dimension reduction from V to \hat{V} ensures us that we can apply Lemma 4.9 of [26] similarly
 1093 to the proof of Theorem 2, stating that the number of iterations k needed to approximate the
 1094 optimal cost of $-Q$ on P_Π with precision ϵ can be upper bounded as $k = O\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon^{d^2}}\right)$, with the
 1095 constant depending on d , and the marginals μ, ν . Algorithm 5 represents our strategy to compute
 1096 the 2-Gromov-Wasserstein distance.

1097 The complexity analysis of the proof of Theorem 3 can also be applied, changing d^2 by $d^2 + 1$,
 1098 which yields:

1099 **Theorem 6.** *Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ be discrete measures with bounded support. Algorithm 5 enables us*
 1100 *to approximate $\text{GW}_2(\mu, \nu)^2$ at a precision $\epsilon > 0$:*

- 1101 - with complexity $O\left(\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)^{2(d^2)(\lfloor (d^2+1)/2 \rfloor + 1)}\right)$,
- 1102 - with memory of size $O\left(\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)^{(d^2)(\lfloor (d^2+1)/2 \rfloor + 1)}\right)$,

1103 where the implied constants depend on d and the distributions μ, ν .

Algorithm 5 Algorithm to approximate the 2-GW cost in dimension d

Require: $\epsilon > 0, \mu, \nu$.

- 1: Compute $C_0 = \int \|x_1 - x_2\|^4 d\mu^2 + \int \|y_1 - y_2\|^4 d\nu^2 - 4 \int \|y\|^2 d\nu \int \|x\|^2 d\mu$
 - 2: Define $f_{i,j} := (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d} \mapsto x^i y^j$ and $V = \text{span}((f_{i,j})_{i,j})$
 - 3: Compute $(\hat{e}_{i,j})_{i,j}$ orthonormal basis of \hat{V} (Algorithm 4).
 - 4: **We run the following steps on \hat{V}**
 - 5: Define bounding boxes $P_{\Pi}^+ := \{\}, P_{\Pi}^- := \{\}$, box cost $c^- = +\infty, c^+ = -\infty$ and optimal direction $\bar{g} = \emptyset$
 - 6: **Initialization of the bounding boxes:** $P_{\Pi}^-, P_{\Pi}^+, c^-, \bar{g}$ (Algorithm 7)
 - 7: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \text{concave_min}(P_{\Pi}^+, -Q)$
 - 8: **Updating bounding box until convergence**
 - 9: **while** $|c^+ - c^-| > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 10: Solve problem (5) (alternatively (10)) given x^+ and compute optimal direction g
 - 11: Solve problem (4) and compute \hat{g}, g^*
 - 12: $P_{\Pi}^- \leftarrow \text{conv}(P_{\Pi}^- \cup g^*)$
 - 13: $P_{\Pi}^+ \leftarrow P_{\Pi}^+ \cap H(g)$
 - 14: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \text{concave_min}(P_{\Pi}^+, -Q)$
 - 15: **if** $c^- < -Q(\hat{g})$ **then**
 - 16: $\bar{g} \leftarrow g$
 - 17: $c^- \leftarrow -Q(\hat{g}_k)$
 - 18: **end if**
 - 19: **end while**
 - 20: **Optimal coupling** π^* solving convex problem (9) given \bar{g}
 - 21: **return** $\pi^*, C_0 + 2c^-$
-

1104 Appendix C Convexity of the different costs

1105 In this section we go over the convexity properties of the different costs. We are looking at the
 1106 polynomial cost $-Q_m$ over the domain P_π . For the Inner Gromov-Wasserstein distance, $Q_m = \|\cdot\|_F^2$,
 1107 which is convex. For the Determinant Gromov-Wasserstein distance, $Q_m = \det$, which is non-convex
 1108 non-concave. Let's go over the Chiral Gromov-Wasserstein distance, depending on the dimension
 1109 d . For $f : \mathbb{R}^{d^2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we denote $H_e(f)$ its Hessian and $\text{eig}(M)$ the set of eigenvalues of the matrix
 1110 M . In the CGW case, $Q_m(x) = t\|x\|_F^2 + (1-t)d!\det(x)$.

- 1111 1. For $d = 1$, $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $Q_m(x) = t\|x\|_F^2 + (1-t)x$, which is convex for $0 < t \leq 1$.
- 1112 2. For $d = 2$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and $\text{eig}(H_e(\|\cdot\|_F^2)) = \{2\}$ and $\text{eig}(H_e(\det(\cdot))) = \{-1, 1\}$. Thus, Q_m is
 1113 convex for $\frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1$, else it is not.
- 1114 3. For $d = 3$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^9$ we still have $\text{eig}(H_e(\|\cdot\|_F^2)) = \{2\}$. The Hessian of the determinant is
 1115 sparse and only contains 4 terms per row and per column. Moreover, all terms are ± 1 times
 1116 a coordinate of the vector x in its canonical basis. Thus, if $\|x\|_\infty \leq r$, then $\text{eig}(H_e(\det(x))) \subset$
 1117 $[-4r, 4r]$. Brute force numerical experiments show that if $\|x\|_2 \leq r$, then $\text{eig}(H_e(\det(x))) \subset$
 1118 $[-\alpha r, \alpha r]$, with $\alpha \sim 1.2$. Now, let σ_μ, σ_ν the standard deviation of μ, ν then we can upper
 1119 bound elements of the cross covariance matrix:

$$\|\Sigma^\pi\|_F^2 = \sum_{i,j} \left(\int x^i y^j d\pi \right)^2 \leq \sum_{i,j} \int |x^i|^2 d\pi \int |y^j|^2 d\pi = \int \|x\|^2 d\mu \int \|y\|^2 d\nu \leq R^2,$$

1120 and thus:

$$\|\Sigma^\pi\|_\infty \leq R^2.$$

1121 with R such that $\text{supp}(\mu) \subset \mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R)$ and $\text{supp}(\nu) \subset \mathcal{B}_0^{\mathbb{R}^d}(R)$. Note that this upper bound
 1122 can be attained, with a typical example in 1D: $\mu = \nu = \frac{1}{2}\delta(-R) + \frac{1}{2}\delta(R)$ and $\pi = (\text{id}, \text{id})\# \mu$.
 1123 Finally, we can choose $t \geq \frac{24R^2}{2+24R^2}$ such that $Q_m(x) = t\|x\|_F^2 + 6(1-t)\det(x)$ stays convex
 1124 on P_π . We can also upper bound our experimental constant yielding : $t \geq \frac{8R^2}{2+8R^2}$. The
 1125 parameter t can also be chosen after the bounding boxes have been initialized, typically by
 1126 upper bounding the vertices infinite norm (in the $f_{i,j}$ basis) of P_π^+ by a number r , and setting
 1127 $t \geq \frac{24r^2}{2+24r^2}$. This ensures that the cost is concave.

1128 Here is a table recapitulating the costs properties and convexity of $-Q_m$:

Cost	Convexity	dimension	t
IGW	Concave	all	
DGW	Non-convex, non-concave	all	
CGW	Concave	1	$0 < t < 1$
	Concave	2	$\frac{1}{2} \leq t < 1$
	Non-convex, non-concave	2	$0 < t < \frac{1}{2}$
	Concave	3	$\frac{24R^2}{2+24R^2} \leq t < 1$
	Non-convex, may not be concave	3	$0 \leq t \leq \frac{24R^2}{2+24R^2}$

Table 1: Convexity of the different costs, for marginals contained in a centered ball of radius R .

Appendix D Algorithm, concave cost

Here is a way to initialize the bounding boxes to ensure the convergence rate of Theorem 2:

Algorithm 6 Bounding box initialization

- 1: Choose e_1 unit vector of V
 - 2: Solve problem (4) and compute $\hat{g}_{\pm 1}, g_{\pm 1}^*$ with direction $g = \pm e_1$
 - 3: $S_1^1 \leftarrow \{x \in V, \langle x, e_1 \rangle \leq \hat{g}_1\} \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, -e_1 \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{-1}\}$
 - 4: $S_1^2 \leftarrow \{\hat{g}_{-1}, \hat{g}_{+1}\}$
 - 5: $S_1^3 \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 6: **for** $k \in [2, d^2]$ **do**
 - 7: Choose e_k unit vector of V orthogonal to the affine subspace containing S_{k-1}^2
 - 8: Solve problem (4) and compute $\hat{g}_{\pm k}, g_{\pm k}^*$ with direction $g = \pm e_k$
 - 9: $g^+, g^- \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}, \operatorname{argmin}(|\langle g_{+k}^* - \hat{g}_{+1}, e_k \rangle|, |\langle g_{-k}^* - \hat{g}_{+1}, -e_k \rangle|)$
 - 10: $S_k^1 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^1 \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{+k}\} \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, -e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{-k}\}$
 - 11: $S_k^2 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^2 \cup g^+$
 - 12: $S_k^3 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^3 \cup g^-$
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: $P_{\Pi,0}^+ \leftarrow S_{d^2}^1$
 - 15: $P_{\Pi,0}^- \leftarrow \operatorname{conv}(S_{d^2}^2 \cup S_{d^2}^3)$
 - 16: **return** $P_{\Pi,0}^-, P_{\Pi,0}^+$
-

Now we state the formulation of the bounding box initialization when Q_m is concave, enabling one to know the optimal direction g^- and cost c^- .

Algorithm 7 Bounding box initialization

```

1: Choose  $e_1$  unit vector of  $V$ 
2: Solve problem (4) and compute  $\hat{g}_{\pm 1}, g_{\pm 1}^*$  with directions  $g = \pm e_1$ 
3:  $c^- \leftarrow \min(-Q_m(g_1^*), -Q_m(g_{-1}^*))$ 
4: if  $-Q_m(g_1^*) \leq -Q_m(g_{-1}^*)$  then
5:    $\bar{g} \leftarrow e_1$ 
6: else
7:    $\bar{g} \leftarrow -e_1$ 
8: end if
9:  $S_1^1 \leftarrow \{x \in V, \langle x, e_1 \rangle \leq \hat{g}_1\} \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, -e_1 \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{-1}\}$ 
10:  $S_1^2 \leftarrow \{g_{-1}^*, g_{+1}^*\}$ 
11:  $S_1^3 \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
12: for  $k \in [2, d^2]$  do
13:   Choose  $e_k$  unit vector of  $V$  orthogonal to the affine subspace containing  $S_{k-1}^2$ 
14:   Solve problem (4) and compute  $\hat{g}_{\pm k}, g_{\pm k}^*$  with direction  $g = \pm e_k$ 
15:    $S_k^1 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^1 \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{+k}\} \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, -e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_{-k}\}$ 
16:    $g^+ \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}(|\langle g_{+k}^* - g_{+1}^*, e_k \rangle|, |\langle g_{-k}^* - g_{+1}^*, -e_k \rangle|)$ 
17:    $g^- \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}(|\langle g_{+k}^* - g_{+1}^*, e_k \rangle|, |\langle g_{-k}^* - g_{+1}^*, -e_k \rangle|)$ 
18:    $S_k^2 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^2 \cup g^+$ 
19:    $S_k^3 \leftarrow S_{k-1}^3 \cup g^-$ 
20:   if  $c^- > \min(-Q_m(g_k^*), -Q_m(g_{-k}^*))$  then
21:     if  $-Q_m(g_k^*) \leq -Q_m(g_{-k}^*)$  then
22:        $\bar{g} \leftarrow e_k$ 
23:        $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(g_k^*)$ 
24:     else
25:        $\bar{g} \leftarrow -e_k$ 
26:        $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(g_{-k}^*)$ 
27:     end if
28:   end if
29: end for
30:  $P_{\Pi,0}^+ \leftarrow S_{d^2}^1$ 
31:  $P_{\Pi,0}^- \leftarrow \operatorname{conv}(S_{d^2}^2 \cup S_{d^2}^3)$ 
32: return  $P_{\Pi,0}^-, P_{\Pi,0}^+, c^-, \bar{g}$ 

```

1133 We now describe a practical initialization for the bounding boxes. This method does not ensure
 1134 the convergence rate of Theorem 3, but it seems to yield good convergence in practical applications.

Algorithm 8 Bounding box initialization (alternative)

Require: e_1, \dots, e_{d^2} orthonormal basis of V .

```

1:  $S_0^+ \leftarrow V$ 
2:  $S_0^- \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:  $c^- = +\infty$ 
4: for  $k \in [1, d^2]$  do
5:   Solve problem (4) and compute  $\hat{g}_{d^2+1}, g_{d^2+1}^*$  with direction  $g = e_k$ 
6:    $S_k^+ \leftarrow S_{k-1}^+ \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_k\}$ 
7:    $S_k^- \leftarrow S_{k-1}^- \cup \{g_k^*\}$ 
8:   if  $c^- > -Q_m(g_k^*)$  then
9:      $\bar{g} \leftarrow g$ 
10:     $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(g_k^*)$ 
11:   end if
12: end for
13: Solve problem (4) and compute  $\hat{g}_k, g_k^*$  with direction  $g = -\frac{1}{d} \sum_1^{d^2} e_i$ 
14:  $S_k^+ \leftarrow S_{k-1}^+ \cap \{x \in V, \langle x, e_k \rangle \leq \hat{g}_k\}$ 
15:  $S_k^- \leftarrow S_{k-1}^- \cup \{g_k^*\}$ 
16: if  $c^- > -Q_m(g_k^*)$  then
17:    $\bar{g} \leftarrow g$ 
18:    $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(g_k^*)$ 
19: end if
20:  $P_{\Pi,0}^+ \leftarrow S_k^+$ 
21:  $P_{\Pi,0}^- \leftarrow \text{conv}(S_k^-)$ 
22: return  $P_{\Pi,0}^-, P_{\Pi,0}^+, c^-, \bar{g}$ 

```

1135 We present the algorithms used in practice to compute the GW_m cost, under the concavity
 1136 assumption. The initialization of the bounding boxes and the choice of direction for the cut do
 1137 not allow us to apply Theorem 3, but the algorithm seems to perform similarly or better than
 1138 Algorithm 1 on simple examples.
 1139

Algorithm 9 Main algorithm for GW_m in dimension d , concave cost

Require: $\epsilon > 0, \mu, \nu$.

- 1: Compute covariance matrix $\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu, \tilde{\Sigma}^\nu$
 - 2: Define: $f_{i,j} := (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d} \mapsto x^i y^j$
 - 3: Define bounding boxes $P_\Pi^+ := \{\}, P_\Pi^- := \{\}$, box cost $c^- = +\infty, c^+ = -\infty$ and optimal direction $\bar{g} = \emptyset$
 - 4: **Initialization of the bounding boxes:** $P_\Pi^-, P_\Pi^+, c^-, \bar{g}$ (Algorithm 8)
 - 5: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \text{concave_min}(P_\Pi^+, -Q_m)$
 - 6: **Updating bounding box until convergence**
 - 7: **while** $|c^+ - c^-| > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 8: Solve problem (10) given x^+ and compute optimal direction g
 - 9: Solve problem (4) and compute \hat{g}, g^*
 - 10: $P_\Pi^- \leftarrow \text{conv}(P_\Pi^- \cup g^*)$
 - 11: $P_\Pi^+ \leftarrow P_\Pi^+ \cap H(g)$
 - 12: $c^+, x^+ \leftarrow \text{concave_min}(P_\Pi^+, -Q_m)$
 - 13: **if** $c^- < -Q_m(\hat{g})$ **then**
 - 14: $\bar{g} \leftarrow g$
 - 15: $c^- \leftarrow -Q_m(\hat{g}_k)$
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: **end while**
 - 18: **Optimal coupling** π^* solving convex problem (9) given \bar{g}
 - 19: (Optional) π^*, c^- solving Frank-Wolfe(m, μ, ν, π^*)
 - 20: **return** $\pi^*, Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\mu) + Q_m(\tilde{\Sigma}^\nu) + 2c^-$
-

1140 **Appendix E Frank-Wolfe line search for the IGW, DGW**
 1141 **and CGW problems**

1142 In this section we explicitly describe the line search optimization step in the Frank-Wolfe algorithm
 1143 **3**, with the IGW and DGW costs. The IGW line search can be written

$$T, \tau = \max, \operatorname{argmax}_{\tau \in [0,1]} \tau^2 \|\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\|_F^2 + (1 - \tau)^2 \|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2,$$

1144 which is convex, yielding solutions at 0 or 1. We have thus the following line search:

Algorithm 10 Line search for IGW

1: **if** $\|\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\|_F^2 > \|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2$ **then**
 2: $\tau \leftarrow 1, T \leftarrow \|\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\|^2$
 3: **else**
 4: $\tau \leftarrow 0, T \leftarrow \|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|^2$
 5: **end if**
 6: **return** T, τ

1145 For the DGW cost, we want to solve

$$T, \tau = \max, \operatorname{argmax}_{\tau \in [0,1]} \det(\tau \Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} + (1 - \tau) \Sigma^{\pi_k}).$$

1146 In dimension 2, we use the fact that, for two square matrices of the same size,

$$\det(A + B) = \det(A) + \det(B) + [\operatorname{tr}(A)\operatorname{tr}(B) - \operatorname{tr}(AB)],$$

1147 such that

$$\det(\tau \Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} + (1 - \tau) \Sigma^{\pi_k}) = \tau^2 \det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + (1 - \tau)^2 \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \tau(1 - \tau)[\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k})].$$

1148 We can write the objective as a polynomial $q(\tau) := \alpha\tau^2 + \beta\tau + \gamma$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k}), \\ \beta &= \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - 2\det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}), \\ \gamma &= \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}). \end{aligned}$$

1149 For the CGW cost with parameter t , we get similarly:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= t[\|\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\|_F^2 + \|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2] + (1 - t)[\det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k})], \\ \beta &= -2t[\|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2] + (1 - t)[\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - 2\det(\Sigma^{\pi_k})], \\ \gamma &= t[\|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2] + (1 - t)[\det(\Sigma^{\pi_k})]. \end{aligned}$$

1150 In dimension 3, we can compute the polynomial such as:

$$\det(\tau \Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} + (1 - \tau) \Sigma^{\pi_k}) = \alpha\tau^3 + \beta\tau^2 + \gamma\tau + \delta := q(\tau).$$

Algorithm 11 Line search for the DGW and CGW problems (2D)

Require: q

- 1: **if** $\alpha \geq 0$ **then**
 - 2: **if** $q(1) > q(0)$ **then**
 - 3: $\tau = 1$
 - 4: **else**
 - 5: $\tau = 0$
 - 6: **end if**
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: $\lambda \leftarrow -\frac{\beta}{2\alpha}$
 - 9: $\tau \leftarrow \min(1, \max(0, \lambda))$
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: $T \leftarrow q(\tau)$
 - 12: **return** T, τ
-

1151 In practice, we can write:

$$\det(A + B) = \det(A) + \det(B) + \frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(A) - \operatorname{tr}(A^2))\operatorname{tr}(B) + \frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(B) - \operatorname{tr}(B^2))\operatorname{tr}(A) - (\operatorname{tr}(A) + \operatorname{tr}(B))\operatorname{tr}(AB) + \operatorname{tr}(A^2B + AB^2),$$

1152 such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\tau \Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} + (1 - \tau) \Sigma^{\pi_k}) &= \tau^3 \det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + (1 - \tau)^3 \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \\ &+ \tau^2(1 - \tau) \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2 \Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right] \\ &+ \tau(1 - \tau)^2 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

1153 Finally, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \\ &- \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2 \Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right] \\ &+ \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

1154

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= 3 \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2 \Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right] \\ &- 2 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

1155

$$\gamma = -3 \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(\operatorname{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \operatorname{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2))\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right].$$

1156

$$\delta = \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}).$$

1157 Finally, we want to maximize q over $[0,1]$, with

$$\frac{dq}{d\tau} = 3\alpha\tau^2 + 2\beta\tau + \gamma.$$

1158 The optimization is the following:

Algorithm 12 Line search for the DGW and CGW problems (3D)

Require: q

```

1:  $A \leftarrow \mathbf{True}$ 
2:  $\Delta \leftarrow 4\beta^2 - 12\alpha\gamma$ 
3: if  $\Delta > 0$  then
4:    $\lambda \leftarrow \frac{-2\beta - \sqrt{\Delta}}{6\alpha}$ 
5:   if  $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$  and  $q(\lambda) > q(0)$  and  $q(\lambda) > q(1)$  then
6:      $\tau \leftarrow \lambda$ 
7:      $A \leftarrow \mathbf{False}$ 
8:   end if
9: end if
10: if  $A$  then
11:   if  $q(0) \geq q(1)$  then
12:      $\tau = 1$ 
13:   else
14:      $\tau = 0$ 
15:   end if
16: end if
17:  $T \leftarrow q(\tau)$ 
18: return  $T, \tau$ 

```

1159 Similarly for CGW(t):

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha = & \det(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \\ & - \left[\frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2)) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2 \Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right] \\ & + \left[\frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2)) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} (\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

1160

$$\begin{aligned} \beta = & t [\|\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\|_F^2 + \|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2] + (1-t) 3 \det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \\ & + (1-t) \left[\frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) - \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2)) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) + \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}})^2 \Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right] \\ & - 2(1-t) \left[\frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2)) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} (\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}} \Sigma^{\pi_k}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

1161

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma = & -2t[\|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2] - 3(1-t)\det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) \\ & + (1-t)\left[\frac{1}{2}(\text{tr}^2(\Sigma^{\pi_k}) - \text{tr}((\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2))\text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}) + \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})^2) - \text{tr}(\Sigma^{\pi_k})\text{tr}(\Sigma^{\hat{\pi}_{k+1}}\Sigma^{\pi_k})\right] \end{aligned}$$

1162

$$\delta = t\|\Sigma^{\pi_k}\|_F^2 + (1-t)\det(\Sigma^{\pi_k}).$$

1163

In this case we can also use Algorithm 12.

1164 Appendix F Supplementary Numerical Experiments

1165 In this section we present results from numerical experiments studying the convergence rate of
1166 our algorithms. In all Figures 4, 5 and 6, marginal points were randomly drawn from a standard
1167 Gaussian distribution and assigned with same weight.

1168 In Figure 4, we evaluated the complexity in the number of vertices and constraints in respectively
1169 the upper and lower bounding box as well as the certificate of global optimality $|c^+ - c^-|$. Our
1170 results suggest, in both dimension 2 and 3 that the complexities in the size of the bounding box
1171 are below the theoretical complexity evaluated in Theorem 3.

1172 Figure 5 represents the convergence of Algorithm 3 in term of cost (squared cost error) or in
1173 term of transport plan (plan error). In both cases of the IGW and the DGW costs, the algorithm
1174 converges in less than 30 iterations.

1175 In Figure 6, we compared two methods (ours and Ryner's [35]) for selecting the new bounding
1176 box cut. Both strategies have similar convergence rates, and their relative performances depend
1177 on the number of points and the desired precision. Typically, Ryner's method tends to alternate
1178 between plateaus and large improvements of the cost, but the algorithm may stagnate indefinitely,
1179 probably due to machine imprecision. In contrast our method tends to have a marginally slower
1180 convergence, with a continuous decrease in cost. In the experiments we performed, the number
1181 of vertices in the outer bounding box behaved differently, between Ryner's and our method. In
1182 the first case this number is quadratic as a function of the iterations, whereas it is linear in our
1183 case, allowing for a larger number of iterations for a given memory. Furthermore, we note that our
1184 method converges exactly in finite (exponential) time for discrete measures with a finite number
1185 of points, whereas such guarantee does not hold using Ryner's method. This is specially useful for
1186 marginals with a low number of points.

1187 **Appendix G** **Supplementary Figures**

Figure 3: Lower and upper bound convergence for the global optimization concave algorithm, when computing the CGW cost in Figure 2A. More precisely c^- and c^+ bound the optimal value of Q_m on P_{Π} . The lower bound c^- converges faster than the upper bound c^+ , which is a recurrent behaviour in our simulations.

Figure 4: Convergence of the global optimization concave algorithm for the IGW cost. A) Convergence in dimension 2 with 5000 points in each marginal. An upper bound on the number of vertices in P_{Π}^+ and the number of constraints in P_{Π}^- is $O(k^2)$, with k the number of iterations. In practice, those numbers have a lower complexity, with a linear behaviour in this case. $|c^+ - c^-|$ is an upper bound of the precision at which the global solution is approximated (see algorithm 2). In dimension 2, an ordinary laptop can run several thousand iterations of the algorithm without suffering memory issues. B) Convergence in dimension 3, with 10 points in each marginal. An upper bound on the number of vertices in P_{Π}^+ and the number of constraints in P_{Π}^- is $O(k^4)$, with k the number of iterations. The blue dashed line represents the function $y = \alpha x^3$ with $\alpha = 1.3$, suggesting that the number of vertices and constraints has a $O(k^3)$ growth in practice.

Figure 5: Convergence of the Frank-Wolfe scheme (Algorithm 3) in dimension $d = 3$, with 1000 points in the marginals. Plan error corresponds to the Euclidean 2-norm between the final transport plan, and the transport plan at each iteration. The cost error similarly corresponds to the difference between the final squared cost and the squared cost at each iteration. A) Algorithm running with the concave **IGW** cost, which simplifies the line search (see section E). B) Algorithm running with the **DGW** cost. In practice, the algorithm converges quickly with both costs, typically under 50 iterations.

Figure 6: Convergence of the global optimization concave algorithm for the **IGW** cost, using two different strategies for selecting the search direction at each iteration. A) Convergence using our strategy, using the P_{Π}^+ facet facing x^+ . B) Convergence of Ryner's strategy [35], using the gradient of Q_m at x^+ .